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E-competences and IT professionalism

ESCOGPT: ESCO search help through GPT embeddings

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the development of a system to identify relevant competencies from the ESCO framework through the application of natural language processing (NLP) techniques and vector embeddings. OpenAI's embedding model is integrated with a vector database to map user input to competencies stored within the ESCO database. The system processes input descriptions by converting them into vector representations, enabling efficient searches within the database. By aligning the input competencies with the stored data, the system demonstrates its potential to improve the accuracy and consistency of competency identification, offering a valuable tool for enhancing educational and professional frameworks.

Keywords: ESCO, GPT, Embeddings, Skills, NLP.

INTRODUCTION

In today's increasingly global and competitive labour market, competitiveness presents a significant challenge for both companies and workers. Employers have access to a wide range of job portals, such as Monster and Infojobs, which aggregate key job listing across various fields. However, the diversity of existing expressions used to define requirements for the same job position often complicates the assessment of a candidate's suitability. This lack of standardization in how skills are described, can hinder employee mobility between companies, both nationally and internationally, and also complicates the search for training programmes that ensure the acquisition of required skills.

This issue extends to the education sector, a fundamental pillar in the development of the skills necessary to perform the job-related competently. In response to these challenges, several

European initiatives have emerged in recent years, primarily aimed at the professional sector. Notable examples include the European job classification from the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) [1], and the European standard EN16234-2021 e-CF [2] promoted by the European Commission.

Although these initiatives are predominantly focused on the professional world, their content can be applied to the academic sphere, as education is a crucial precursor to acquiring the knowledge required for employment. Therefore, while the ultimate goal is centred on the labour world, we seek to evaluate the integration of these initiatives with the academic world, with the aim of developing a tool capable of identifying ESCO competences through Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. This tool would facilitate the identification of competencies in educational resources by using a common language based on established reference frameworks.

This article is organized as follows: first, it will be examined the key elements that comprise this work. Next, it will be presented the research conducted followed by the conclusions drawn from the study.

BACKGROUND

To develop this project, it was essential to conduct a preliminary study of the elements most influential to its progress. This section provides a brief summary of the research carried out concerning the ESCO Framework, the use of vector Embeddings and vector databases.

ESCO

In recent years, several European initiatives have emerged focused on defining, characterizing and assessing the competencies of professionals, students and citizens. Among the most important are frameworks such as ESCO¹ and e-CF².

Within these competency frameworks, ESCO (European Skills Competences and Occupations), supported by the European Commission, offers a comprehensive taxonomy of 3,008 occupations and 13,890 competencies. These figures are constantly evolving as ESCO undergoes continuous revisions. The primary goal of ESCO is to standardise the identification of skills and competences at a professional level. This standardisation aims to establish a coherent and uniform system that ease the identification of workers' skill gaps and training needs, making them better suited for specific job position. Moreover, ESCO enhances communication between the education and employment sectors supporting geographic and occupational

¹ https://esco.ec.europa.eu/es/classification/skill_main

² <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/es/node/193>

mobility across Europe. It stands out as a fundamental tool in helping professionals adapt to the ever-changing demands of the labour market.

Vector embeddings

To create a program capable of interpreting the requested information, vector embeddings are employed. This technique generates a vectorial representation of data, significantly simplifying similarity searches conducted by machine learning models. Unlike traditional text analysis methods, which typically relied on word frequency, vector embedding capture both semantic and contextual relationships, improving the understanding of natural language and increasing the efficiency of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques.

In this project, OpenAI's text-embedding-3-small model was utilised, which transforms text into a vector with a dimensionality of 1,536. The decision was made to use a single embedding model to evaluate its feasibility in the development of the tool.

Vectorial Database

A vector database stores information as mathematical representations, a common approach in Machine Learning as it enables the recognition of previous entries and improves search performance. In this case, the vector database used is ChromaDB³, an open-source application database that works with embeddings and vector searches.

For this project, the information stored in the database of each ESCO skill includes id, metadata, values and embeddings. The "id" is a unique code used in ESCO to identify the skill; "metadata" refers to the skill title; "value" is the textual description of the skill and "embeddings" are the vector representations based on OpenAI's model.

The query process within the dataset functions as a ranking system, returning the values whose embeddings are most similar to the text being searched.

RESULTS

Once each component of the system has been studied, the next step was to set up an architecture capable of searching for the most similar ESCO competencies. To achieve this, the system will include an interface where the user can input a description of the desired competency. The system then uses an OpenAI API⁴ call to generate the corresponding

³ <https://www.trychroma.com/>

⁴ <https://openai.com/index/openai-api/>

embedding. This embedding is subsequently used to perform a search within the ChromaDB database. Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the developed system.

Figure 1. Architecture of the program

To validate the obtained results, we used the teaching guide from a course in the Computer Engineering degree programmes of the University of Alcalá title “Databases”. This guide contains a list of the competences that students are expected to acquire throughout the course. Initially, the search was conducted in the same language as the stored competences, English. Some of the results obtained are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Resultados de búsqueda de competencias

Database Competence	ESCO Competence
Ability to conceive, write, organize, plan, develop and sign projects in the field of computer engineering that are intended, in accordance with the knowledge acquired	Plan, organize, control and document procedures and resources, such as human capital, equipment and mastery, in order to achieve specific goals and objectives related to ICT systems, services or products, within specific constraints, such as scope, time,
Ability to design, develop, evaluate and ensure accessibility, ergonomics, usability and security of computer systems, services and applications, as well as the information they manage.	Apply guidelines related to securing access and use of computers, networks, applications and the computer data being managed.
Ability to conceive, develop and maintain computer systems, services and applications using software engineering methods as an instrument for quality assurance, in accordance with the knowledge acquired	Use software tools (CASE) to support the development lifecycle, design and implementation of software and applications of high-quality that can be easily maintained.
Ability to define, evaluate and select hardware and software platforms for the development and execution of computer systems, services and applications, in accordance with the knowledge acquired	The technologies and standards to be used during the installation, deployment and maintenance of software characteristics.

As shown, the results closely align with the intended meaning of the competencies. This prompted the next test, where we used the Spanish definition to evaluate whether the system could perform a multi-language search. During these tests, it was found that the results varied

with a notable outcome when searching for Spanish terms such as in “Capacity of analysis and synthesis”, which returned the competency “Read and comprehend written texts in Spanish”.

Given this result, we introduced the possibility of returning up to 5 search results. In many cases, the top results in both languages matched, with some more relevant results appearing in later positions according to the embeddings. This demonstrates that, to improve the tool’s effectiveness, users should be provided several options to select the most suitable result for their research query.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The use of embeddings in search engines improves the quality of results considering not only the word appearance, but also the semantics and meaning of the text. However, using embeddings as an identification tool, as done in this project, requires expert analysis to ensure accuracy and a detailed analysis. Nevertheless, the results presented here demonstrate that such tools can significantly enhance the identification of stored elements. In this case study, the system was able to narrow the search from over 13,000 references, underscoring its potential as a valuable tool for future developments. The results also highlighted the importance of offering multiple results to provide users with more search options.

Having validated the effectiveness of embeddings for identifying ESCO competencies, we plan to explore new analysis techniques and compare different embedding models to assess which offers the best performance.

This article presents results from the project titled “Integración de GPT en la transferencia de competencias en el marco laboral”, funded by the call for grants for the implementation of projects for the transfer and exchange of knowledge and innovation of the University of Alcalá.

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A Scoping Literature Review Design for Mapping the Relation between Twin Transition Maturity Levels and Skills

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a research design for a scoping review linking the skills required for Twin Transition to maturity levels in Twin (i.e. digital plus Sustainability) Transformation growth. This review can help businesses identify their organisational capabilities and strategise which skills their staff need to develop toward the next Twin Transition maturity level. The authors also hypothesise that Twin Transition maturity development trajectories may be identified.

Keywords: Twin Transition, Dual Transformation, Digital Transformation, Sustainability Transformation, Maturity Model, Maturity Level, Skills, Competences

INTRODUCTION

This paper builds upon a literature review that identified relevant competences and skills for the twin transition, conducted in the context of an EU-funded Digital4Sustainability project. We argue that further analysis of the identified competences (knowledge, skills and attitude) is necessary, based on the level of business maturity in both digital and sustainable transformation, together referred to as "Twin Transformation"). This analysis helps businesses to identify its organisational capabilities. Subsequently, it may help them strategise on which skills the staff need to grow toward the next maturity level. Therefore, it is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of the emergent concept of Twin Transition in relation to the skills *per Twin*

Transition maturity level. To address this need, we propose a scoping review design to explore this relationship between Twin Transition and maturity levels in Sustainable and/or Digital Transformation . Furthermore, we hypothesise the twin transformation may have different pathways of growth in digital and sustainable transformation, resulting in different needs in skills and competences per maturity level. In this paper, we discuss the design of the scoping review and some preliminary results.

TWIN TRANSITION BACKGROUND

Skills and Competences

As a starting point for this paper, we adopted the European Commission's definition of competences. Where competences are described as an integrated set of knowledge, skills and attitudes [1]:

- Knowledge consists of established theories, concepts, facts and figures contributing to understanding a given subject.
- Skills comprise manual and cognitive abilities to put acquired knowledge into practice.
- Attitudes represent a mindset or tendency to behave or react in a particular way in a particular context.

Digital and Sustainability Transformation combined into Dual or Twin Transition

The Digital Transformation concept has many definitions in extant literature. Based on an extensive literature review in the field of information systems, Vial [2] suggests the following definition: digital transformation is "*a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies*". This definition is not organisation-centric and incorporates improvement as an "*expected outcome of digital transformation without guaranteeing its realisation*" and is not associated with any specific digital technology. Another definition of Digital Transformation focuses on value rather than 'improvement', created by the fundamental change brought about by digital technologies, for both internal and external stakeholders [3]. These authors are more organisation-centric in their definition.

Similarly, sustainability transformation has many definitions. Sustainability finds its origin in the commonly used definition of sustainable development [4], stating that we should meet the needs of the present human population, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [5] which all include addressing ecological, economic, or social goals [3]. Digital transformation and sustainability transformation are both transformative processes that

bring changes in processes, products, and business models. Digital technologies may enable sustainability potentials, whereas sustainability puts some constraints on the firm's use of digital technologies [4]. More specifically, "*digitalisation of business activities can be directed towards sustainability but requires a shift towards sustainability-defined visions and goals.*" [5].

The Dual or Twin Transition refers to "*a transformation approach that holistically and strategically combines both digitalisation and sustainability in the firm in order to leverage synergies and manage mutual interdependencies in the best possible way*" [4]. In this definition we see an organisation-centric focus, and the transformative nature of the two separate transitions is included. Besides this, it can be noted that '*the best possible way*' refers to both the '*added-value*' or '*improvement*' of the earlier discussed digital transformation, as well as it refers to '*sustainability*' in its purest form, the ability to sustain for a long term.

Maturity Models for Twin Transition or Digital or Sustainable Transformation

A digital transformation maturity model can 1) provide the ability to (self-)assess an organisation's digital capabilities and 2) identify the growth trajectory for further developing these digital capabilities [6]. Likewise, a sustainability maturity model provides this in terms of sustainability capabilities. Many models are so-called fixed-level maturity models that distinguish four or five maturity levels, for example the well-known CMM for digital capabilities [7]. The number of maturity levels and the names of each maturity level vary for digital or sustainable transformation maturity models. Often, four or five levels of maturity are distinguished in these models. De Bruin et al. [8] argue that maturity models come in three distinct varieties:

- 1) a descriptive model (understanding the as-is situation),
- 2) a prescriptive model (through the understanding of current situation pathways to possible improvements),
- 3) a comparative model (potential to compare with other organisations when the model is in use widely).

Maturity models typically have three distinct components for a suggested evolutionary path to reach the intended maturity level, where a maturity level is a well-defined evolutionary plateau within a functional domain [7, 9]. These components are:

- 1) a descriptor of maturity levels (such as initial, repeatable, defined, managed, and optimised);
- 2) focus areas or dimensions, (these can be developed to achieve the defined maturity levels);
- 3) detailed descriptions and suggestions for improvements (actions) .

Below, in table 1 the maturity levels used in the CMM model are presented for illustrative purposes. In this example it shows a descriptive model. This model gives an description of five maturity levels (descriptor -component), gives distinct differences between these levels (focus

area -component) but, it does not explained detailed actions on how to achieve the next maturity level (detailed improvements– component).

Table 1. Example of A five-tiered maturity level scheme.

Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively managed	Optimised/ Transformed
<i>Processes poorly controlled and reactive</i>	<i>Processes characterised for projects are often reactive</i>	<i>Processes characterised by the organisation and are proactive</i>	<i>Processes measured and controlled</i>	<i>Focus on process improvement</i>

Missing link? Skills (Levels) for Twin Transition per Twin Transition Maturity Level

We observed a gap in the literature during the earlier named literature review identifying relevant competences and skills for the twin transition for the EU-funded Digital4Sustainability project. The relationship between the needed Twin Transition competencies and maturity levels is rarely directly discussed. Therefore, we suggest conducting a scoping review. This review combines the extant literature on twin transitions with the extant literature on the organisation’s competences needed to develop its organisational capabilities from one maturity level to the next one.

PROPOSED METHOD FOR SCOPING LITERATURE REVIEW

The proposed method for conducting this research is a scoping review. This method is suitable for the stated research question in the emergent field of twin transition, as a scoping review is 'useful for mapping the literature on evolving or emerging topics and identifying gaps. It may be a step before undertaking research or conducting another type of review, such as a systematic review' [10, 11]. Table 2 describes the steps of the scoping review.

The first step is to identify the suitable Maturity Models for Twin Transition or separately for Digital and Sustainability Transformation. The expected outcome of this first step is a generic description of maturity levels in Twin Transition, both on the axes of Sustainability and Digital Transformation. After comprising this Twin Transition maturity model, we proceed with the analysis of the literature on competences. In this second step we aim to link identified competences associated with twin transformation to the comprised maturity model, mapping and clustering these competences accordingly. This may show emergent maturity-level-specific skills needs.

We use the literature collected on competences for twin transformation in the Digital4Sustainability project. This literature is screened by scholars involved in the project,

focusing on information related to maturity levels in Twin Transition. The aim of this second step is to identify clusters of competencies categorised per maturity level. The third and final step entails collating, summarising, and reporting the results. The expected outcome is a strategic roadmap for competences development based on growth trajectories in Twin Transition maturity development.

Table 2. Proposed steps for conducting the scoping review

Step	Action	Expected Outcome
Step 1: Formulation Twin Transition Maturity	Formulate search query, inclusion and exclusion criteria for literature review on the state-of-the-art on the concepts of Twin Transition or Dual Transformation Maturity Models. This query will include relevant main Information Systems or Sustainability journals: ("dual transformation" OR "twin transition" OR "twin transformation" OR (digital sustainable transformation)) (maturity level) OR "readiness assessment") This may be slightly broadened to include Digital Transformation Maturity Models and Sustainability Transformation Maturity Models that look appropriate for mapping required skills (competences) to certain maturity levels. We primarily focus on peer-reviewed academic literature. Depending on the scarcity of the results for this emergent topic, we will extend the search to include industry papers and reports.	The result may be a preliminary choice for a specific model or a synthesis of maturity models that is the starting point for mapping skills (or competences in a broader sense) to either sustainability or digital transformation maturity levels. Expected outcome: a generic description for maturity levels in Twin Transition, both on the axes of Sustainability as well as Digital Transformation
Step 2: Identifying Relevant Studies on Skills (Competences) for Twin Transition (Dual Transformation)	Colleagues of the Digital4Sustainability project have conducted a literature review on skills for Twin Transition [12]. The peer-reviewed articles of that study will be screened based on maturity levels regarding sustainability, digital transformation, or both. Additionally, the sources of step 1 will be screened on skills and added to the results.	This enables us to build upon insights of the thematic analysis on skills for twin transition and map these skills or clusters of them on maturity levels for sustainability or digital transformation. Expected outcome: identification of (clusters) of skills or broader competencies per maturity level.
Step 3: Collating, Summarising, and Reporting the Results	The mapping of skills on Twin Transition maturity levels will be analysed, and the hypothesis of Trajectories for Twin Transition will be evaluated.	Expected outcome: this enables us to create a strategic roadmap for skills (competences) development based on growth trajectories in Twin Transition maturity development.

We now briefly explain the hypothesis we propose for our scoping review.

HYPOTHESIS FOR MAPPING THE FINDINGS: TRAJECTORIES FOR TWIN TRANSITION

We expect that the scoping literature review may reveal clusters of knowledge, skills and attitudes (competences), and the amount of these competences, that can be ascribed to a certain

level of maturity, either for the sustainability transformation or the digital transformation. Furthermore, the scoping review could reveal different pathways for growth at the Twin Transition maturity level (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Trajectories for Twin Transition

We suspect some firms will initially set out with a growth trajectory mainly focused on sustainability maturity development and later catch up with their digital transformation development (Initially sustainability-focused). Other firms will prefer a growth strategy that starts with growth in digital transformation and later increases their sustainability maturity level (Initially digitalisation-focused). Lastly, firms may choose a trajectory in which sustainability and digital transformation maturity grow at more or less the same pace (Intermediate trajectory). We suspect that firms in the same industry sector may have similar preferred trajectories that can be associated with these three groups.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

An initial query and analysis of articles resulted in this short list of papers that cover the twin transition in combination with maturity levels, to be discussed in more detail at the ICODSIP 2024 conference.

All articles confirm the importance of maturity levels for twin transformation, as the end goals cannot be reached without a series of stages for organisational development. Most articles have a pre-determined set of maturity levels, often based on other sources. The number of twin transition (TT) maturity levels ranges from three to six [13, 14]. Even in this relatively small number of articles, Three articles describe the Intermediate trajectory in which the maturity development in both sustainability and digital transformation follows the same pace [15-17].

Table 3. Preliminary results of the scoping review.

Article	ID	TT maturity levels	Twin Transition Pathways
Breiter et al. (2024)	[15]	4	Intermediate trajectory
Van Erp and Rytter (2023)	[16]	5	Intermediate trajectory <i>Circular (sustainable) vs Digital Transformation</i>
Uhrenholt (2022)	[13]	6	Initially sustainability-focused <i>Towards circular sustainability</i>
del Socorro et al. (2024)	[17]	5	Intermediate trajectory
Christmann et al. (2024)	[14]	3	Intermediate trajectory
Spaltini, Acerbi et al. (2024)	[18]	Undetermined	Intermediate trajectory
Martínez-Peláez et al. (2024)	[19]	Undetermined	Initially digitalisation-focused.

Two articles highlight the circular business model as the top, most mature stage of the sustainability transformation side of this twin transformation [13, 16]. We found one article describing the Initially sustainability-focused trajectory developing towards circular sustainability [13] and one article describing the pathway for Initially digitalisation-focused, developing into sustainable digital transformation [19]. The analysis is ongoing, and preliminary results will be presented at the conference.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We presented a research design for a scoping review linking the skills required for Twin Transition to maturity levels in digital or sustainability transformation growth, including some preliminary results. Our hypothesis on various trajectories for twin transition is already visible in the preliminary results. The next step is conducting the full scoping review and analysis of the results. This would contribute to our knowledge of the firm's Twin Transition and the capabilities needed to make that possible. The authors expect to present preliminary findings of this review at the ICODSIP 2024 conference. The EU partially funds this study for the Digital4Sustainability project under grant nr. 101140316 (Call: ERASMUS-EDU-2023-PI-ALL-INNO).

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Bridging the Advanced Digital Skills Gap in Europe: Recommendations for Academia, Industry and Policy Makers

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ABSTRACT

The LEADS project, funded under the DIGITAL Programme, aimed to address the advanced digital skills (ADS) gap across Europe. Through a comprehensive market analysis of over 150 use cases and more than 1,100 STEM-related courses, the project identified significant disparities between ADS demand and supply, in emerging fields such as AI, IoT, and Cybersecurity. Engaging over 250 stakeholders through workshops, and as results of a qualitative analysis process validated through multiple iterations and discussions, LEADS developed 51 targeted recommendations to address the ADS gap across five key areas: holistic ADS training, comprehensive curriculum design, effective training delivery, facilitated skills acquisition, and expansion of the training offer. This paper details these findings, focusing on the ten primary recommendations deemed critical for addressing the ADS gap.

Keywords: Advanced digital skills (ADS), ADS gap, ADS demand, ADS supply, Digital Decade

1. INTRODUCTION

The Digital Compass developed under the Digital Decade Strategy¹ includes the ambitious target for reaching 20 million ICT specialists employed in the EU by 2030 having in mind a greater gender convergence. Facing the ADS gap across Europe, the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) (2021-2027) is an EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to

¹ Europe's Digital Decade: digital targets for 2030 – European Commission, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en

businesses, citizens and public administrations. It provides strategic funding to answer these challenges, supporting projects in key capacity areas such as: High-Performance Computing, Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Advanced Digital Skills, and ensuring a wide use of digital technologies across the economy and society. Among the projects funded by the Digital Europe Programme, LEADS (Leading Europe's Advanced Digital Skills²) was funded in the context of the Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) of the Digital Decade, in relation to skills across 21 months (from October 2024 to June 2024). It was a Coordination and Support Action tasked with providing data, analysis, foresight and guidance on the demands for advanced digital skills across Europe by the end of the decade to support the definition of Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) actions to be funded under the Digital Europe Programme.

To achieve this, LEADS performed a market data-driven analysis process to create the ADS Framework with the technologies, skills and job roles considered under the project umbrella. Technologies selected include Cloud technologies, Business Intelligence and Data Science, Security technologies, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things [1]. A detailed demand assessment and forecasting analysis was performed for each technology based on tracking over 150 use cases in the corresponding technologies [2]. These results were cross-referenced with existing ADS course availability (1,100 ADS courses were scrutinised), combined with expert stakeholder engagement across several workshops, events and roundtables, to provide a deep analysis of the ADS demand/supply gap [3].

This paper presents the main recommendations generated by the LEADS project to cover the ADS gap resulting from the outcomes of eight workshops that engaged more than 447 participants from different ADS contexts, including education providers, industry and policy makers. We will focus on the top 10 primary recommendations identified by the audience as the ones with major impact on addressing the ADS supply/demand challenges. These recommendations are aimed at fostering a dynamic and responsive educational landscape.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the main challenges identified from the gap analysis in as leading questions that motivated the resulting workshops. Section 3 describes the process to identify the resulting recommendations, and Section 4 provides an overview of these recommendations focusing on the top 10 primary action points according to their expected impact in addressing the ADS gap. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. ADS DEMAND/ANALYSIS CHALLENGES

The ADS gap analysis performed during the project led to the identification of different challenges that need to be addressed to cover the increasing ADS demand that will be produced in the future. We have reformulated these challenges into five top leading questions which are delved into a deep analysis and discussion, as they become crucial to cover the corresponding gap:

² <https://advancedskills.eu/>

- **How can we design a comprehensive strategy to allow integration across pathways in vocational training (VET) and higher education (HE) courses?** Even when up-skilling and re-skilling will take a relevant role in ADS talent provision [4], HE and VET will need to provide the bulk of the training required. To ensure that demand is adequately covered, alignment and cooperation between both domains are essential. HE provides long-term programmes based on well-founded knowledge and prepares students with learning skills for quick adaptation. On the other hand, VET graduates are trained through shorter programmes in very specific, practical and up-to date problems ideally driven by industry demand. Additionally, graduates will need to improve and develop new skills during their professional road for which the VET offer will be essential. In sum, the strategy to align both domains needs to be defined to include dynamic industry demands and to provide a holistic framework for ADS learning.
- **How can education and training meet the demands for advanced digital skills?** Development of curricula that remain adaptable and relevant in the face of rapid technological evolution. Additionally, previous results have highlighted the need for embedding real-world, problem-solving abilities into the curriculum to better prepare students for the challenges they will inevitably face once they transition to the workforce. The role of industry in this process is essential both as identifiers of ADS needs as well as, as real-world experience providers to improve the students learning process.
- **How to ensure the availability of appropriately recognised micro-credentials, short-term course and online learning options to meet industry and learner demands?** The concept of micro-credentials has emerged as a key element to cover the existing industry demand of ADS. The dynamic evolution of ADS knowledge requires a continuous and lifelong learning up-skilling and re-skilling process. Additionally, the provision of micro-credentials integrated into university programmes will contribute to provide students with the recognition of their knowledge prior to their final degree. The challenge is how to define those micro-credentials so as the knowledge acquired during this process is recognised by industry, and, on the other hand, how to make it available in a flexible way so practitioners can combine their professional practice with the learning process.
- **How can Generative AI revolutionise ADS Curriculum Development and Learning Support Systems, propelling education into a new era?** Limited resources in education, and in particular the lack of ADS teaching talent, is one of the existing challenges. In this context, new innovative learning methods need to be used to teach ADS knowledge efficiently. The use of AI and in particular, generative AI in education was gaining attention as an innovative learning method with huge potential. However, important challenges such as bias in training data, ethical considerations, and the need for careful implementation should be considered when applying this tool.
- **Is it possible for universities to overcome structural challenges and barriers to respond to the needs of advanced digital skill development? Is there a role for policy to support reforms in the HEI sector or change the expected roles for universities?** Universities play a crucial role in the effort to cover the ADS demand [5]. They have a relevant pool of workforce, knowledge and infrastructures to face skilling in a trusted way motivated by

academic excellence. However, they also have a rigid structure and are guided by strict administrative and regulatory rules, both at national and regional level. These controls limit HEs flexibility to quickly adapt to the ADS dynamic changes and knowledge, as well as to define the required collaboration with industry and other training providers. This top leading question raises the existing challenges faced by universities to this respect in search of potential ways to overcome such challenges in a flexible way.

3. APPROACH FOR GENERATING RECOMMENDATIONS TO COVER THE ADS GAP

Workshops served as the primary qualitative data collection method to gather insights on the previous challenges. Over eight workshops, involving more than 250 stakeholders - education providers (mainly universities and VET providers), demand providers (primarily from industry), and education enablers (policy makers at national and EU level) - were organised facilitating open discussion and generating actionable recommendations to address the raised issues.

Two qualitative data analysis methods—thematic analysis and content analysis—were used to process the data from these workshops. Thematic analysis, guided by open coding and the identification of key themes [6], was applied to each individual workshop to develop each set of recommendations. To synthesize the findings across all workshops, content analysis helped us to group the recommendations into key areas and into clusters based on their objectives.

Overall, the synthesis of all recommendations was an iterative process involving discussions and consensus-building among project partners to ensure clarity and coherence across all recommendations. The detailed process is shown in [7].

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ADDRESSING THE ADS GAP CHALLENGES

The previous process yielded a set of 51 individual recommendations. Figure 1 shows an overview of such recommendations encapsulated around five key areas:

- **Holistic ADS training landscape:** Meeting the demand for ADS requires a multifaceted approach to training, incorporating diverse avenues such as HE, VET, in-house company courses, short-term courses, and specialist training programmes. Therefore, skilling, upskilling, and reskilling are imperative to bridge the ADS gap effectively. However, it is crucial to clearly define the skills to be provided at each level of training. Additionally, flexible pathways are essential for transitioning among these levels.
- **Comprehensive and flexible ADS body of knowledge:** To cope with highly evolving skills: the delivery of effective ADS training requires precise identification of the knowledge required by ADS professionals. This preparation is crucial to enable them to adeptly tackle diverse industrial projects requiring ADS expertise, collaborate effectively within various teams, and be equipped to embrace continuous learning throughout their careers.
- **Effective ADS delivery:** Ensuring effective ADS training also entails careful consideration of the most impactful training methods. Additionally, special attention must be paid to the

availability and training of ADS trainers. Their proficiency is pivotal in delivering high-quality training that effectively equips learners with the necessary skills and knowledge in the rapidly evolving field of ADS.

- **Supporting/facilitating ADS acquisition:** Efforts are imperative to ensure accessibility to ADS training for individuals who desire or require it. This involves implementing initiatives and programmes that remove barriers to entry and provide opportunities for individuals to access the necessary training, regardless of their background or circumstances.
- **Fostering the ADS training offer:** Expanding the range of available ADS training offerings is essential to meet the anticipated demand for ADS skills. By diversifying the training options and increasing their availability, we can better address the growing need for skilled professionals in the digital domain.

Complementarily, recommendations have been structured around the stakeholder who has the major role in their implementation, even when the participation of other roles might be crucial to perform the recommendation satisfactorily. Figure 1 also shows with double background the recommendation clusters, grouping individual recommendations with a similar aim. One pocket might be addressed under different areas and different actors, so it might be repeated in Figure 1. In addition, Table 1 shows the number of recommendations identified by key area, distinguishing between primary and secondary recommendations. Primary recommendations are those collectively agreed on by the partners as actions with a greater impact on the ADS gap.

Table 1. Number of recommendations by topic and relevance

Key Area	Primary recommendations	Secondary recommendations
Holistic ADS training landscape	3	16
Comprehensive and flexible ADS body of knowledge	3	4
Effective ADS delivery	1	8
Fostering the ADS training demand	1	10
Fostering the ADS training offer	2	3
In total	10	41

Primary recommendations serve as central focal points to address the challenges posed by the ADS gap comprehensively. As can be seen in Table 2, they encompass all key areas and involve all stakeholders, policymakers, education providers, and industry representatives. For each recommendation an indication of its time frame is provided. Additionally, a reference to the workshop or workshops from which the recommendation was gathered is included.

Table 2. ADS Principal recommendations

Key Area	Main actor	Recommendation	Description	Source	Time
Holistic ADS Training Landscape	Policy Makers	Regulate and promote flexible ADS training pathways	Allow and define flexible pathways between HEI and VET inter level, transdisciplinary and interprofessional (e.g., VET students continue studies in university, holders of a degree in Humanities to ICT specialization, etc.)	Workshop 5 Workshop 8	Middle-term
		Define periodic assessment of ADS training initiatives	These assessments ensure that the training content remains current, relevant and aligned with global industry needs	Workshop 4 Workshop 6	Middle-term
		Create frameworks that facilitate the seamless transferability of skills acquired through micro-credentials	Governments can collaborate with industry stakeholders to establish systems that recognize and value micro-credential-acquired skills across educational institutions and industries.	Workshop 6	Middle-term
		Implement a skills-focused education	Prepare curricula to address the corresponding skill-focus profile to which industry is moving. Establish a continuous feedback loop with industry for curriculum definition (use Advisory Boards as tools to drive such collaboration).	Workshop 5	Middle-term
Comprehensive and flexible ADS body of knowledge	Education providers	Foster strong collaborations with industry partners	Collaborations provide valuable insights into current and emerging needs, establishing a feedback loop with industry professionals. Regular input ensures that ADS training aligns with job market requirements, offering ongoing assessment of programme relevance and effectiveness. This feedback aids in timely adjustments to course content and delivery methods.	Workshop 1 Workshop 2 Workshop 4 Workshop 5 Workshop 6	Short-term
		Design courses with a strong emphasis on practical, hands-on application	Include guest lectures, real-world projects, case studies, and simulations to ensure that learners acquire practical skills that are directly transferable to their professional role.	Workshop 1 Workshop 4 Workshop 5 Workshop 6	Short-term
Effective ADS delivery	Policy Makers	Promote a learner centered delivery approach	Knowledge needs to be provided in a more agile way and in a learner centred delivery structure. For example, online classes, weekend courses, afternoon courses, hybrid/blended courses, are also options to be considered to allow learners to access courses.	Workshop 5 Workshop 6	Middle-term
Fostering ADS training demand	Industry	Implement incentives for lifelong learning: Rewards upskilling and reskilling	Encourage employers to value ongoing ADS development, creating a culture that recognizes and rewards individuals who proactively engage in upskilling and reskilling initiatives	Workshop 5 Workshop 6	Short-term
Fostering ADS training offer	Policy Makers	Provide incentives for micro-credential programmes creation.	Provide incentives, such as grants or tax benefits, to educational institutions engaged in developing innovative and industry-relevant micro-credential programmes.	Workshop 6	Middle-term
		Urge the national governments to support universities to target short-cycle tertiary ADS programmes and re-skilling masters.	These funds should be additional to the funds currently devoted to skilling and up-skilling	Workshop 1	Middle-term

5. CONCLUSION

The aim of the LEADS project to bridge the existing ADS gap is highly relevant in the current digital era, as the ADS demands continues to grow across all sectors of the economy. Addressing this skills gap is crucial for the EU to meet its ambitious target of 20 million ICT specialists by 2030, as well as to maintain its competitive edge in the global digital landscape. By providing data-driven insights and stakeholder-driven recommendations, our work offers a strategic blueprint for policymakers, educators, and industry leaders to collaboratively improve the ADS ecosystem. Overall, the various recommendations gathered emphasise a multi-faceted approach to bridging the ADS gap, including flexible pathways, industry-aligned curricula, learner-centred delivery methods, incentives for continuous learning and supportive policies. Together, these recommendations aim to create a dynamic and responsive educational landscape that meets the evolving demands of the digital age.

A continuation action has been funded, Leading Europe's Advanced Digital Skills to 2030 (LEADSx2030) to provide a platform for knowledge-sharing and best practice dissemination, ultimately fostering a robust digital ecosystem that empowers European industries and individuals to thrive in the Digital Decade to continue working on the ADS.

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DIGITAL4Business: European Online Master's Programme in Advanced Digital Skills

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INTRODUCTION

The EU has recognised the critical need to bridge the growing gap in advanced digital skills to ensure its global competitiveness. By 2030, 20 million ICT professionals will be required to meet the demands of an increasingly digital economy. However, only 9 million individuals currently possess the necessary competencies across the 27-member states [1].

DIGITAL4Business is a 20M Euro EU-funded project to address the increasing digital skills gap, focusing on SMEs and Multinational Organisations. Its objective is to develop a flexible, online Master's programme that focuses on the practical application of advanced digital skills such as Cybersecurity, Artificial Intelligence, Cloud Computing, and Data Science. It combines academic accreditation with industry-recognised certifications to ensure practical relevance and empower professionals with the digital capabilities to meet current and future challenges in technology-driven fields.

WORK PACKAGES

WP1 Project Management and Partnership: Ensures effective coordination and collaboration among consortium members. It covers all project management tasks, quality assurance, and long-term partnerships with academic institutions and industry.

WP2 Needs Analysis and Programme Design: Identifies gaps in advanced digital skills across the EU27 and determines which competencies are most in demand in SMEs and Corporates. This analysis has informed the curriculum design, ensuring that the programme focuses on the areas with the highest market relevance.

WP3 Programme Development and Platform Setup: Creates the Master's-as-a-Service platform, leveraging the Microsoft Azure ecosystem. The platform provides a robust environment for delivering educational content, student engagement, and certification processes.

WP4 Programme Rollout and Delivery: Manages student recruitment, enrolment, and support of students. The programme is offered full-time and part-time, with additional workshops, hackathons, and industry networking events.

WP5 Dissemination and European Impact: Focuses on communication and dissemination of the project results, ensuring its impact throughout Europe.

WP6 Long-Term Sustainability: Focuses on expanding partnerships with additional higher education institutions and industries. The aim is to ensure a sustainable model for delivering advanced digital skills across Europe.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

Systematic Needs Analysis: Yielded important insights into digital skills in Europe [2], namely:

- Cybersecurity and Cloud Computing emerged as the most critical skills for SMEs, while larger companies place higher importance on AI and Data Science.
- The digital divide between large enterprises and SMEs remains a concern, with smaller firms facing significant barriers to adopting new technologies like Big Data and Cloud Services.

Programme: Recently accredited as a joint European degree, it has been developed as a flexible and scalable online curriculum offering relevant courses and industry-recognised certifications. Underpinned by the systematic needs analysis which utilised both desk research and surveys, targeting industry stakeholders from SMEs and multinational corporations.

Sustainability: The long-term viability is ensured through WP6, which focuses on expanding partnerships with additional higher education institutions and industries. The aim is to provide a sustainable model for delivering advanced digital skills across Europe.

Platform: A state-of-the-art cloud-based framework integrates digital teaching tools that efficiently underpin learning, teaching, and student support.

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The European Software Skills Alliance (ESSA) and Artificial Intelligence Skills Alliance (ARISA) Projects

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INTRODUCTION

ARISA¹ (co-funded by Erasmus+ Project: 101056236 — ERASMUS-EDU-2021-PI-ALL-INNO) and ESSA² (co-funded by Erasmus+ “Blueprint” Project n. 2020 – 621751-EPP-1-2020-1-BE-EPPKA2-SSA-B) are closely aligned projects that share a consortium of partners and complementary objectives. Due to their synergy, we are presenting them together. Both projects tackle Europe’s pressing digital skill shortages, with ARISA focusing on artificial intelligence (AI) skills and ESSA on software skills. Together, they aim to develop specialized skill sets tailored to the growing demands of the digital workforce.

ESSA and ARISA at a glance

The ESSA project, launched in November 2020 and with a four-year duration, aims to skill, upskill, and reskill individuals for in-demand professional software roles across Europe. It achieves this by offering comprehensive, open-license educational and training tools to learners, training providers, and organizations.

Two years later, in 2022, the twin project ARISA was launched. It has a similar mission but focuses on AI-related skills. ARISA goes beyond addressing the skills gap for AI developers; it also empowers business leaders and policymakers with the knowledge to navigate and drive the AI revolution effectively.

¹ Discover the full alliance here: <https://aiskills.eu/the-alliance/>

² Discover the full alliance here: <https://softwareskills.eu/network/>

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

ARISA and ESSA follow a similar Work Package structure (see Figure 1). This begins with a skills needs analysis (WP2), which presents the current supply and demand of skills, as well as identifies existing skills gaps. Next is the development of a European Skills Strategy (WP3), outlining the various steps needed to address these gaps. Building on this, the projects design educational profiles and learning programs (WP4), which are then piloted at the national level by higher education institutions (HEIs) and vocational education and training (VET) partners in the consortia (WP6). To ensure the market competitiveness of these learning pathways, the programs and pilots are supported by the development of quality labels and micro-credentials (WP5).

Figure 1: Structure of ARISA and ESSA.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

ESSA and ARISA projects have significantly addressed skills gaps in their respective fields. ESSA has conducted a comprehensive [Needs Analysis](#), developed a [European strategy for Software skills](#), and designed **educational profiles using e-CF and ESCO** that developed into 14 [Learning Programmes](#) and Train the Trainers programs. Through the piloting, the project has skilled, upskilled, and reskilled more than **300 students** and involved **80 educational professionals**.

Similarly, ARISA has advanced AI skills development by producing a [Sector Skills Analysis](#), establishing the [AI Skills Strategy for Europe](#), and creating **14 AI curricula** for profiles such as data scientists, machine learning engineers, and AI advisors. ARISA will also carry out a CEN Workshop Agreement as one of the tools to ensure the project's sustainability.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The ESSA and ARISA projects have contributed substantially to addressing critical digital skills gaps in Europe. ESSA successfully developed a comprehensive strategy for software skills development, delivering key outcomes such as a needs analysis and pilot training programs across various countries. Similarly, ARISA has made significant strides in advancing AI skills by creating a standardized curriculum, launching the ARISA Quality Label, and promoting a strategic approach to AI upskilling and reskilling.

The European Network of Cybersecurity Skills Hubs (CyberHubs)

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INTRODUCTION

[CyberHubs](#) (co-funded by Erasmus+, Project: 101140030 — ERASMUS-EDU-2023-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP — Alliances for Education and Enterprises) aims to enhance the cybersecurity professional skills ecosystem in Europe by establishing a network of 7 Cybersecurity Skills Hubs (a.k.a. CyberHubs) in Belgium, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Spain, which will promote cybersecurity professional skills development and support the development of a skilled cybersecurity professional workforce in the short, mid and long term.

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

CyberHubs' work package structure allows for a stepwise approach in analysing the status and progress of cybersecurity professional skills and roles needs across the 7 countries, leveraging best practices, establishing and nurturing a community of CyberHubs actors and beyond, and delivering high-value services and awareness-raising activities to the communities across the 7 countries. Alignments between the CyberHubs are fostered and nurtured thanks to European frameworks such as ECSF and e-CF which ensure common terminology and shared understanding, among other benefits.

Figure 1. CyberHubs work package structure

CyberHubs and European frameworks

Across the work packages, ENISA's [European Cybersecurity Skills Framework](#) (ECSF), which presents 12 cybersecurity professional role profiles and integrates e-CF competences from the [European e-Competence Framework](#) (EN16234-1) in each role, provides a practical tool to support the identification and articulation of tasks, competences, skills and knowledge associated with the roles of European cybersecurity professionals. In CyberHubs, the ECSF provide a common understanding of the main cybersecurity missions, tasks and skills needed in a professional cybersecurity context, making it a valuable reference for profiling skills and knowledge needed by cybersecurity professionals. More specifically, the CyberHubs are conducting country-specific Needs Analysis on cybersecurity skills and roles based on the 12 ECSF profiles, as a starting point. As part of the multi-method approach, i) the job vacancy analysis extracts skills from the job posting data against different roles and job titles, ii) the desk research focuses, among others, on establishing a review of articles on ECSF and related frameworks, iii) the expert panels help to discuss all the ECSF roles and associated skills and discuss their relevance and need in the national context.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

The first important result of the project, the cybersecurity professional roles and skills needs analysis carried out in 7 European countries, helps to understand which of the ECSF 12 cybersecurity profiles are of particular demand in each country, together with the most demanded skills. The [CyberHubs dashboard](#) (updated every six months) reflects the first results of the job vacancy analysis gathered in 2024. This dynamic dashboard offers at a glance valuable insight as to the most looked after ECSF mapped jobs and skills, i.e., in Spain, the Cybersecurity implementers are the most in-demand, and incident and project management are two of the most critical skills. At the end of October 2024, the 7 national Needs Analysis reports will be made available. These results will be translated in a next step into national cybersecurity strategies, backed by a forecasting model allowing for regular updates on cybersecurity professional roles and skills needs on national levels with a solid connection to the broader European digital and cybersecurity context.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

CyberHubs contributes substantially to addressing the lack of cybersecurity professionals the need for a whole-of-society approach to tackling cybersecurity issues to ensure Europe's digital resilience. It proposes a solid *CyberHubs* model for increased collaboration and the development of cybersecurity education, training, and workforce development.

EdTech Talents: Evidence from secondments in widening countries

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INTRODUCTION

The EdTech Talents project fosters cross-sectoral talent circulation and collaboration between academia and businesses in Estonia, Hungary, and Serbia. It aims to enhance education and technology by facilitating knowledge exchange with successful EdTech companies in Austria, Germany, and Spain. The project offers guidance and training to strengthen connections between education and business sectors. It is funded under the Horizon Europe program (ID: 101119689) as part of the HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03 call. The EdTech Talents project involves various academic and industry partners: Tallinn University (Coordinator), University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Obuda University, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Rey Juan Carlos University, Bielefeld University, EdTech Center Western Balkans, EDUCATION:NEXT, EdTech Estonia, BLINC EG, Lurtis Rules SL, and MatheArena GmbH. Each partner brings unique expertise in education, technology, and innovation to foster cross-sectoral collaboration.

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

EdTech Talents project consists of four work packages (WP) occurring in seven phases (Figure 1). **WP1** focuses on the administrative and financial management of the project, ensuring successful coordination and long-term sustainability of the developed network. **WP2** organizes the secondment of researchers from widening countries (Estonia, Hungary, and Serbia) to advanced countries (Austria, Germany, and Spain), pairing them with companies that offer mentoring and support to turn their ideas into marketable EdTech services. **WP3** coordinates the secondments of researchers from advanced to widening countries, fostering mentoring relationships that demonstrate how companies can benefit from academic knowledge services. **WP4** focuses on sharing knowledge from secondments and coordinating communication efforts to maximize the project's impact on academia, businesses, policymakers and society.

Figure 1. EdTech Talents project in a nutshell

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

In this first year we have been working in establishing the most appropriate methodology for the developing secondments, and overcoming the limitations we have detected, mostly related to identifying the needs of the participating companies that could be met during the implementation of this project.

Efforts in the second year of implementation are focused on developing an effective dissemination plan, as well as working on the design and development of knowledge sharing events with impact on the different stakeholders of the Project

CONCLUSION

The goal of the EdTech Talents project is to strengthen academia/non-academia cooperation and reinforce the EdTech innovation ecosystems of Estonia, Hungary and Serbia by conducting a long-term knowledge transfer process for (a) the researchers and their support staff of these widening countries to learn from the EdTech spin-offs and consulting companies of Austria, Germany and Spain; and (b) the researchers of these advanced countries to share their relevant intellectual capital with the EdTech start-ups of these widening countries.

During the development of the project, knowledge transfer is supported via dedicated mentoring and training that aim at establishing continuous and more impactful flow of innovation, ideas, knowledge, know-how and relevant services among all involved, corresponding with the scope of ERA Policy Agenda and ERA Talents call for cross-sectoral talent circulation and academia business collaboration, with the focus on widening countries.

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Digital competence and skills

Reboot Skills: co–design for demand of digital skills in job market

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ABSTRACT

Digitalization is transforming the job market at an unprecedented pace, necessitating a skilled workforce capable of innovating and adapting in a rapidly evolving professional landscape. This shift presents a challenge for education systems to rethink competence-building processes to align with emerging digital demands. Traditional degree-centric models of education are increasingly inadequate for addressing the ongoing needs for reskilling and upskilling in the workforce. This paper explores how higher education can integrate into the fast-paced ecosystem of professional skill development and examines the role of co-design methodology in analyzing the demand for digital skills in the job market. Through a single-case study, this research investigates how co-design approaches can bridge the gap between the practical needs of the job market and the academic perspectives on future digital competencies. This study addresses a critical research gap by offering insights into effective methodologies for aligning educational practices with evolving digital skill requirements.

Keywords: Co-Design, Digital Skills, higher education

INTRODUCTION

Digitalization affects nearly all areas of life, including the job market, with rapid changes expected to continue. These changes demand a skilled workforce capable of innovating, adapting, and creating value in a dynamic environment. As digital technologies evolve, competence-building processes must also adapt, along with how we learn, leading to new digital learning environments.

This paper explores how higher education institutions can adapt to the fast-paced development of professional skills. Traditionally focused on degree programs, universities now face the challenge of addressing reskilling and upskilling for professionals already in the workforce. The study investigates how co-design methodology can help analyze the demand for digital skills in the job market, addressing the gap between industry needs and academic perspectives on future digital skills.

This paper answers a research question “How can co-design be implemented to advance analysis of demand of digital skills in job market?” through a single-case case study. The research question addresses a gap in research on the methodologies for bridging the practical needs of the job market with the research-based vision of higher education institutes on what will be the relevant future digital skills needed at the job market.

BACKGROUND

World Economic Forum Future Jobs Report from 2020 predict that half of all employees worldwide would need reskilling by 2025 [1]. Newly emerging skills especially on technology-related competences are estimated to considerably change the essential skill sets of employees in this decade [2], and most likely beyond. These trends have challenged also higher education institutes to examine their role in evolving competence building environment. Higher education institutes (HEIs) are no longer solely degree program focused, but innovate education models supporting life-long learning, experiential learning with industry, non-degree certificates, for example[2]. This transition from degree program producing organization into life-long learning organizations requires systemic changes at all levels of HEIs.

Using participatory design approaches, such as co-design methods, in learning design has been proposed to support teachers in design choices in ways how to integrate technology into teaching [3]. Involving learners in co-design of education has been noted to improve the quality of education and benefits not only learners, but also teachers in the form of education designs that are better fitted in the context [1] . It has been suggested that adoption of co-design methods is a way for higher education institutes to respond to global competition and pressure to adopt market driven approaches in education [5].

METHODS

The research problem is approached with a single-case case study. The case study explores a collaborative project funded by Digital Europe Programme called REBOOT SKILLS.

The Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) is an EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations. It implements EU's objective to support public and private organisations with upskilling and reskilling, so they can thrive through the green and digital transitions (<https://pact-for-skills.ec.europa.eu/>). REBOOT SKILLS (<https://www oulu.fi/en/projects/rebooting-manufacturing-industry-digitalisation-skill-development>) is a collaboration of five countries and eight organizations in Europe which have come together to strategically build their capacity as individual organizations and as an ecosystem to provide digital skills training for manufacturing industry, aiming specifically small and medium sized companies. The collaboration started in January 2023, and it will continue in the context of Digital Europe umbrella until end of 2025. After that, all organizations will use the strategic competencies they have been building during the project in their operation and continue collaborating as an ecosystem in selected topics.

REBOOT SKILLS designs, delivers and validates short courses and trainings targeted for manufacturing industry about advanced digital skills, for example, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, robotics and manufacturing internet of things. Courses are designed to be accessible for working professionals. Co-design approach is used to tailor the course delivery for each target group and topic; including finding the optimal combination of online and on-site learning methods and the most suitable teaching language to meet the needs of the learners and availability of best expertise.

Data has been collected through an ethnographic inquiry by the people involved in the project activity through the project lifecycle, and it has been collectively analyzed and synthesized by the same people. This approach allows access to rich and detailed empirical material, as the authors of the paper have the lived experience of going through the process of integrating co-design activity into creating an understanding of the needs of the manufacturing industry for digital skills training. However, it must be noted that this approach also has its limitation in objectivity. All authors have personal lived experience of being part of the topic examined. Therefore, the contribution is highly subjective and must be interpreted in this context.

Case description

The Reboot Skills ecosystem was designed to involve partners in relevant roles. The roles were (1) higher education institutes (HEIs) and (2) industrial networking partners.

Four of the partners are traditional higher education institutes in different countries: Finland, Sweden, Belgium and Ireland. The HEIs had different levels of strategic engagement in developing education offering for working professionals.

The four partner organizations operate at the interface of HEIs and the manufacturing industry, offering expertise on building successful collaborations. One partner worked closely with a specific HEI, while others collaborated with multiple HEIs. Two partners actively helped organize training with HEIs, while the other two focused on identifying training needs and facilitating communication between HEIs and the industry, including marketing courses and determining optimal delivery methods.

Data collection and analysis

The authors of this paper were active in designing, planning, organizing and delivering the REBOOT SKILLS training offering from its start. The results are based on experiences on integrating the co-design activity into the project activities from January 2023 until August 2024. All activities have been documented in meeting memos, project deliverables and various communication channels, including emails and social media. This material provides a rich and deep data about practical implementation of co-design protocol into training planning. Material has been analysed primarily in four co-design events as follows:

- Co-design meeting 1: Attractive training for SMEs. As a result a pallet of training opportunities was created.
- Co-design meeting 2: Ecosystem and SMEs needs. As a result, a map of ecosystem stakeholders and their role was defined.
- Co-design meeting 3: Creating Impact and Crediting. As a result, impact framework was created, and accreditation plans were defined.
- Co-design meeting 4: Sustainability. As a result, pathways for how to continue education were outlined.

In these two to three day co-design events, dedicated workshops focusing on specific questions were organized. For example, list of stakeholders (see Results) was a result of a co-design workshop organized in the second co-design event. The co-design workshop facilitated experience sharing and synthesis between the project partners.

RESULTS

To ensure the work life relevancy of the training, the REBOOT SKILLS training model was based on integration of the co-design activity into all phases of the project. The following sections

describe the protocol that was followed in integrating co-design into education planning, and partners involved.

Co-design protocol

The co-design process began with establishing a shared vision through a co-design protocol, guiding activities from training development to final evaluation. The protocol integrates ecosystem involvement throughout the project, led by a team of experts from each REBOOT SKILLS partner organization. This team ensures that training programs align with the needs of the manufacturing industry and tailors the involvement approach based on context.

Co-design methods range from consultations to full co-production, depending on training needs and available resources. Basic involvement includes consultations through meetings, focus groups, and surveys, while deeper involvement involves stakeholders co-producing and delivering training. For example, a company may participate by sharing their experience with application of a certain digital technology in their production line.

Wide range of co-design activities were found to be beneficial, as they allowed co-design partners experience different aspects of the design process. Sometimes the input from manufacturing industry participants was contradictory, for example, in regards the delivery mode. The partners might state that self-paces online teaching would better fit their schedules, but then realize later that face-to-face learning settings support their learning better. One of the hardest design problems in REBOOT SKILLS was how to create training experiences which are accessible for working professionals who constantly struggle with finding time to participate training. Significant amount of co-design effort was spent in finding optimal delivery modes so that the training would be accessible for working professionals.

The success of co-design depends on open collaboration and trust. REBOOT SKILLS fosters psychological safety through workshops and meetings, supported by input from country-specific knowledge of training needs. To further involve SME companies, a budget is allocated for subcontracting experts from the manufacturing industry to help design and deliver training, with quality control overseen by the project partners.

Two boards are set to provide regular contact with external experts on steering the focus and optimal co-design: Advisory Board (AB) and SME Oversight Board (SMEOB). The advisory board members included representatives from different stakeholder categories (education, industry, policy) and SMEOB was constructed with representatives from small and medium enterprises in

manufacturing industry. Both boards were called to meet two to four times annually to discuss matters related relevancy and quality of the training.

Co-design partners

Wide involvement of manufacturing industry ecosystem stakeholders was considered important in future proofing the training. The following seven main stakeholder groups were identified:

- **SMEs and larger organizations:** The manufacturing industry ecosystem is very heterogenous, with both very big multinationals and very small local SMEs. SMEs play a vital role in economic development, job creation, and innovation across various industries. They are characterized by their size, typically with fewer than 500 employees, and generally larger than micro enterprises. Involving both in co-design was considered vital. SMEs often have limited access to affordable training, so they can specifically benefit from training supported by public funding. However, involvement of large organizations can also benefit training as they often set the industry standards and can bring practical experiences in how digitalization can bring value.
- **Research center and innovation clusters:** They are critical primary stakeholder groups that drive advancements in technology, knowledge, and economic development. Research centers serve as hubs for scientific exploration, and discovery across various disciplines, fostering a culture of innovation and academic excellence. Innovation clusters, on the other hand, bring together businesses, research institutions, and other stakeholders in a geographic area to promote collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the development of cutting-edge solutions. Together, these entities play a pivotal role in shaping industries, driving technological progress, and contributing to the overall growth and competitiveness of regions and nations. Their collaborative efforts often lead to breakthroughs, creating a ripple effect that positively impacts economies and societies.
- **HEIs:** They are integral primary stakeholders in the education and knowledge dissemination landscape. These institutions serve as centers of learning, research, and innovation, playing a fundamental role in shaping the intellectual and professional development of individuals. HEIs contribute to the broader community by generating new knowledge through research and offering a diverse range of academic programs. As primary stakeholders, HEIs interact with various entities, ranging from students, researchers to industry partners, and even government agencies. The collaborative efforts of universities with other stakeholders contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge and technology.

- **EDIHs:** European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) are pivotal primary stakeholders in the European digital ecosystem, playing a central role in fostering innovation and digital transformation. As part of the European Union's strategy to boost the competitiveness of businesses and stimulate economic growth, EDIHs act as catalysts for the adoption of digital technologies. These hubs serve as collaborative platforms, bringing together businesses, research institutions, technology experts, and public organizations. Their mission is to facilitate the digitalization of industries by providing expertise, infrastructure, and support for experimentation and innovation. EDIHs contribute to the development of interconnected digital ecosystem, supporting businesses towards the emerging technologies, such as AI, the IoT, and Cybersecurity. Through their efforts, EDIHs propel Europe toward a more competitive, digitally resilient future.
- **Governments and public organizations:** They are foundational primary stakeholders that play a central role in shaping societal structures and providing essential services. Governments, whether at the national, regional, or local level, are responsible for formulating and implementing policies that govern public affairs, economic activities, and social welfare. Public organizations, including regulatory bodies and public services, are instrumental in ensuring compliance with laws, safeguarding public interests, and delivering essential services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. As primary stakeholders, governments and public organizations interact with citizens, businesses, and other entities, aiming to create a stable and equitable environment.
- **European engagements:** It encompasses a diverse and influential array of primary stakeholders that collectively contribute to the economic, political, and cultural integration across Europe. It involves the collaboration of European Union member states, institutions, businesses, and citizens in various projects and collaborations aimed at fostering cooperation, stability, and sustainability. The European Union, as a key player, facilitates and coordinates these engagements, working to address common challenges, and promote collaboration across borders.
- **Industry and business associations:** They form a vital primary stakeholder group that represents the interests, concerns, and expectations of businesses within specific sectors or across industries. These associations play a crucial role in advocating for favorable business environments, influencing policy decisions, and fostering collaboration among various entities. They contribute to the development of best practices, regulatory frameworks, and industry standards. Also, they facilitate networking opportunities, share knowledge, and address common challenges. The collective impact of these associations

extends beyond individual companies, shaping economic landscapes and contributing to the overall growth and sustainability of industries.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The REBOOT SKILLS co-design activity gives a practical overview on integration of co-design activity into the entire lifecycle of a collaborative effort to develop and pilot a competence development model targeted for working professionals. The presented co-design model aims for flexibility across contexts, providing framework to choose the most feasible involvement methods according to local environment and the nature of the topic to be covered. The model also acknowledges different roles of co-design partners, ranging from low involvement activities to ones that require more time and effort.

For comprehensive co-design, recognition of relevant co-design partners is crucial. The results from the REBOOT SKILLS project give an example of how in this specific case study the relevant partners were defined. It is crucial that the co-design protocol takes into account different types of stakeholders, so that they can be optimally integrated into the co-design process.

REBOOT SKILLS project has received funding from EU Digital Europe Program.

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Developing a Digital Competence Framework for Botswana

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ABSTRACT

The development of a Digital Competence Framework (DCF) for the citizens of Botswana is described and discussed. The method of developing the framework was to use the EU DigComp Framework with existing additions by UNESCO and the World Bank as a basis and further adapt it through a programme of stakeholder engagement in Botswana. Approaches to adaptation and the involvement of stakeholders are described with the key inputs summarised on the content and implementation of the DCF. The potential role of digital competence frameworks in enabling wider development goals through managing the positive use of digital technology and reducing the risks is reviewed.

Keywords: Digital Competence Frameworks, Sustainable Development Goals, Botswana, International Development.

INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses a recent project to develop a Digital Competence Framework (DCF) for the citizens of Botswana and investigates its potential as an informative example of internationalising and adapting existing EU frameworks. It was funded by EU Delegation for Botswana and the Southern African Development Community (SADC) and the main partner in Botswana was the 'SmartBots' project team based in the Ministry of Communications, Knowledge and Technology.

The DCF is part of the 'SmartBots' digital transformation strategy developed[1] and run by the government of Botswana aligned with the digital transformation strategy for Africa[2] with very positive hopes and plans for the benefits of digital technology. The digital transformation strategy is part of a wider goal to move Botswana from a middle to a high-income country by 2036[3].

The objectives of the paper are to discuss the following questions using the DCF as an illustrative example:

- What particular issues should be considered when adapting EU digital competence frameworks to different world regions?
- What is the role of digital competence frameworks in contributing to Sustainable Development Goals?

BACKGROUND

Framework adaptation

The method of developing the framework was to use the EU DigComp Framework with existing additions by UNESCO[4] and the World Bank[5] as a basis and further adapt it through a programme of stakeholder engagement in Botswana. The EU DigComp Framework[6] is primarily designed as framework for user digital skills as required by ordinary people rather than professional ICT specialists. This is in contrast to frameworks designed for ICT professionals such as the e-Competence Framework (e-CF)[7] and the Skills Framework for the Information Age (SFIA)[8]. In the development of DCF this distinction was not quite as clear cut as the existing work to internationalise DigComp done by UNESCO and the World Bank had added two new competence areas 0. Devices and Software Operations and 6. Career Related Competences which then move the content into the areas of ICT professionalism. An additional competence 5.5 Computational Thinking had also been added to Competence Area 5: Problem Solving. These are shown in the figure below which includes additions to the DigComp competences.

Figure 1. Digital Competence Framework for Botswana

DIMENSION 1: COMPETENCE AREA	DIMENSION 2: COMPETENCES
<p>0. DEVICES AND SOFTWARE OPERATIONS</p>	<p>0.1. PHYSICAL OPERATIONS OF DIGITAL DEVICES 0.2. SOFTWARE OPERATIONS IN DIGITAL DEVICES</p>
<p>1. INFORMATION AND DATA LITERACY</p>	<p>1.1. BROWSING, SEARCHING AND FILTERING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT 1.2. EVALUATING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT 1.3. MANAGING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT</p>
<p>2. COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION</p>	<p>2.1. INTERACTING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES 2.2. SHARING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES 2.3. ENGAGING IN CITIZENSHIP THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES 2.4. COLLABORATING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES 2.5. NETIQUETTE 2.6. MANAGING DIGITAL IDENTITY</p>
<p>3. DIGITAL CONTENT CREATION</p>	<p>3.1. DEVELOPING DIGITAL CONTENT 3.2. INTEGRATING AND MODIFYING DIGITAL CONTENT 3.3. COPYRIGHT AND LICENCES 3.4. PROGRAMMING</p>
<p>4. SAFETY</p>	<p>4.1. PROTECTING DEVICES 4.2. PROTECTING PERSONAL DATA AND PRIVACY 4.3. PROTECTING HEALTH AND WELL-BEING 4.4. PROTECTING THE ENVIRONMENT</p>
<p>5. PROBLEM SOLVING</p>	<p>5.1. SOLVING TECHNICAL PROBLEMS 5.2. IDENTIFYING NEEDS AND TECHNOLOGICAL RESPONSES 5.3. CREATIVELY USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES 5.4. IDENTIFYING DIGITAL COMPETENCE GAPS 5.5. COMPUTATIONAL THINKING</p>
<p>6. CAREER-RELATED COMPETENCES</p>	<p>6.1. OPERATING SPECIALISED DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR A PARTICULAR FIELD 6.2. INTERPRETING AND MANIPULATING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT FOR A PARTICULAR FIELD</p>

The project objective was to further extend this adapted framework adding more depth to the new competence areas (0 and 6) and competence 5.5 with content for Dimension 3: Proficiency Levels, Dimension 4: Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes and Dimension 5: Examples in Use. Within the European ICT professionalism community there has been much useful work done on formalising the logic and method of developing the content of competence frameworks and other related tools such as ICT Role Profiles[9]and ICT Bodies of Knowledge[10]. Most of the EU frameworks also include methodology sections, user guides and there are also guides on how to integrate their use in practice [11]. There has also been a wider discussion about the role of transversal skills in ICT as well as how to best incorporate (or not) ethical concerns into competence frameworks[12]. In terms of previous work on the use of an African approach to values in digital ethics research has been carried out on the use of Ubuntu[13], a traditional African value system which focuses on togetherness and interdependency on each other guided by the philosophy that “I am because you/we are”[14], to inform digital policy and approaches.

ICT skills in development

The development of ICT skills within a population is clearly no guarantee of economic development but lack of ICT skills can be said to hamper development. The exact nature of these skills and at what level they are required is dependent on context and existing maturity levels[15]. There have been a few initiatives in different African countries to formalise a structured approach to digital skill development[16] and a significant number have adapted and built on existing skills frameworks such as DigiComp[17]. As described in the introduction the adapted version of DigComp developed by the UNESCO and the World Bank can be said to blur the distinction to an extent between professional ICT skills and user skills. The reasoning behind this was to enable it to be useful for people developing employability skills. An additional factor is that the wider population needs to have a baseline of digital skills to provide companies who provide digital based service with customers and digital government services with users.

The growth in digital connectivity is also not wholly positive and provides new opportunities for crime, the exploitation of the young and anti-social activities [18] [19]. DigComp provides some content to help protect users in terms of Competence Area 4: Safety, but wider legal and policy protections also need to be in place.

METHOD

The standard competence framework methodology was used in terms of a literature review and iterative development through stakeholder engagement. Guidance on the appropriate literature and stakeholders was provided by the SmartBots team who also directly organised the in-person training and consultation days. The total stakeholder engagement consisted of 15 online consultations, 3 site visits and 3 days of in-person workshops.

Table 1. Summary of stakeholders consulted

Organisation	Role
Directorate of Public Service Management (DPSM)	Public Service HR strategy
Botswana Public Service College (BPSC)	Delivery and development of Public Service training
Ministry of Education and Skills Development (MESD)	Interpretation of education policies, design, development and evaluation
Botswana Qualifications Authority (BQA)	Maintain and implement the National Credit and Qualifications Framework
The University of Botswana (UB)	Provides professional qualifications and innovation support
The Botswana National Library Services (BNLS)	Provide citizens digital skills training
Internet Society Chapter Botswana (ISOC)	Digital skills training to village development committees (VDCs)
InFuture Trust	Cyber security training for youth
Botswana Digital & Innovation Hub (BDIH)	Attracting international investment in innovation and technology

RESULTS

The input from stakeholders was extensive with some on the content of the DCF itself and some on more general digital policy and skill development issues.

Feedback on DCF content

In terms of DCF the main input was on the necessity of clearly showing the importance of inclusion and ethics in the framework in terms of, for example, inclusion for people with disabilities. It was suggested to build on existing projects in Botswana who were using the African concept of Ubuntu as an appropriate way to conceptualise and communicate the role of ethics. Framework content also often includes images and symbols and some of the DigComp ones, particularly from earlier versions, were quite Eurocentric so this needed to be adapted.

The need for the examples of use and knowledge/skills/attitudes to be appropriate to the different contexts in Botswana was also seen as important. Geographically some areas are very remote, there are problems with extreme heat and sand as well as issues with interruptions to power supplies which poses specific challenges. The content of DCF needs to reflect the different skills and specifically knowledge that are needed in the Botswana context. The table below shows the additions to Competence Area 6.

Figure 2. Dimension 4 and 5 of competence area 6 from DCF

COMPETENCE 6 – WITH DIMENSION 4 (KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, ATTITUDES) AND DIMENSION 5 (USE CASES)		
Table 18: COMPETENCE 6 – WITH DIMENSIONS 4 AND 5		
	<p>DIMENSION 4: KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, ATTITUDES EXAMPLES (NOTE THAT THESE APPLY TO COMPETENCE AREA, NOT TO SPECIFIC COMPETENCES WITHIN A COMPETENCE AREA NOR TO SPECIFIC LEVELS)</p> <p>KNOWLEDGE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.1.1. Knows the different technologies (both hardware and software) that can be used to automate business processes in my working environment 6.1.2. Knows how to use digital technologies to enhance my productivity in the workspace 6.1.3. Knows the current digital skills and tools needed for career options that interest me <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.1.4. Applies knowledge in coming up with innovative tools for data management and analysis for decision-making <p>ATTITUDES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.1.5. Committed to ongoing research and development for enhanced capacity to provide ongoing support to enterprises I am working with 6.1.6. Open to how digital tools could enhance my ability to work in my career 	<p>DIMENSION 5: USE CASES</p> <p>INTERMEDIATE BY MYSELF EMPLOYMENT-JOB SEEKING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I can create an environment for continuous and sustainable knowledge management in order to ensure learning and sustainable marketability on the job even after maturity and retirement. • I can identify business opportunities that can catapult me into continuous contribution to the digital economy. <p>EDUCATIONAL BY MYSELF</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I can pass on knowledge to others and build their capacity to contribute to Vision 2036, leveraging on the digital economy. • I can collaborate with others and provide backstopping support to their innovative digital solutions and to businesses and community members.
<p>DIMENSION 1: COMPETENCE AREA</p> <p>6. CAREER-RELATED COMPETENCES</p> <p>Use specific career-related digital technologies and content to have access to opportunities in the digital economy</p> <p>6.1. OPERATING SPECIALISED DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR A PARTICULAR FIELD</p>		

Finally, the logic of the proficiency levels was sometimes felt to not work equally well for each competence. This was interesting feedback and brought to the fore the occasional tension between consistency and relevance in competence framework design.

Feedback on DCF use and implementation

On the more general digital policy level the strongest message was on the need to integrate the provision of technology with the appropriate training and infrastructure combined with an awareness of the local situation. Providing laptops to schools had produced mixed results with some children suffering violent assault and theft of their laptop on their way to or from school. It can also create inter-generational problems if the wider family is also not involved. It was felt that in some cases a more critical assessment of the potential role of ICT, or not, in education should be used. One participant made the strong point that 'we must not lose who we are' by just going along with the use of digital devices without considering support needed.

In terms of training the public servants, parts of the DCF, in particular those on career focused competences are useful, but would probably also need additional support from existing professional ICT competence frameworks. There is already a range of training opportunities for public servants and DCF should be integrated into existing systems rather than starting new ones. There is a need for high level digital strategy training as well as more technical digital skills and this is not a straightforward problem to solve. The digital skills for start-ups and SMEs are different but could also benefit from input from the DCF.

REVIEW OF OBJECTIVES

What particular issues should be considered when adapting EU digital competence frameworks?

Generally speaking, within any framework as the specificity increases so does the need for adaptation to the new context. Within the WB/UNESCO revised DigComp there were already two new competence areas which did not yet have Dimension 3: Proficiency Levels, Dimension 4: Knowledge/Skills/Attitudes or Dimension 5: Examples in Use, and one new competence 5.5: computational thinking so these dimensions had to be added. For the original DigComp competences the Dimensions 3, 4 and 5 were adapted and edited as necessary. Knowledge, for example, in DigComp includes reference to particular EU legislation or regulation and this needs to be replaced with the equivalent regional content.

What is the role of digital competence frameworks in contributing to Sustainable Development Goals?

There is a role both at the micro and macro level. The stakeholders could see the value of a framework in terms of developing curricula and also at a policy making and monitoring level. There are normally many different initiatives contributing to the SDGs but more coordination through the use of a framework is seen as useful. In general competence frameworks were seen as helpful in building up a holistic capability approach and helping to avoid siloed initiatives.

CONCLUSION

The development of DCF was a very interesting and informative process and also provides new insights into some of the strengths and weaknesses of the original DigComp and digital competence frameworks in general. As Europe becomes increasingly diverse frameworks must be culturally sensitive enough to appeal to a wide audience. Digital Competence Frameworks can be a useful tool globally but adaptations in content and implementation are necessary. The most benefit is gained when they are used in competence development practice and also seen as part of a policy, planning and monitoring tool to assist coordinated and targeted programmes.

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Analysing the DigComp framework and linking it to the non-IT labour market

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ABSTRACT

DigComp has become the main reference in the EU for general digital skills. Its implementation in education and training since version 2.1 has been very wide, frequently connected to funded national or European projects. Its link to the labor market is rather, not especially addressing the needs for professional work. Its flexible nature as framework has also induced a wide range of interpretations of its concepts and competencies. Some of the present developments in learning outcomes could help in giving more guidance to practical application to reality. This work is aimed at performing a specific text/semantic analysis of the components of the framework for additional insights to practitioners as well as a deeper analysis of the link to labor market through the open sources of ESCO labor classification and the OVATE tool.

Keywords: DigComp, digital skills, ESCO, labor market, online job ads

1. INTRODUCTION

The DigComp framework for digital competence has undergone several iterations since its inception, aimed at defining and developing the digital skills needed for citizens to participate effectively in a digital society. DigComp 1.0 [1] was the first version and introduced a basic model of digital competence, structured around the five key areas: Information and data literacy, Communication and collaboration, Digital content creation, Safety, and Problem-solving. The second version DigComp 2.0 [2] refined the framework by detailing 21 competencies across the five existing areas and introduced a proficiency scale ranging from "Foundation" to "Advanced." This version aimed to support both individual users and policy development, integrating a broader societal context into digital competence. A new minor update to DigComp 2.0 was

released as DigComp 2.1 [3]. This version started to emphasize enhancing employability through digital competence. However, the direct link between the framework and the labor market was not clearly presented. As a result, satellite publications like [4] started to reflect on this link although far from clearly analyzing all its aspects. Of course, version 2.1 acted as an ignite of a myriad of initiatives and projects (or even certifications) across Europe, so it is obvious that some of them also studied the link with labor market. This explosion of application of DigComp in practice (especially in education and training) also revealed the flexibility of the framework in parallel with the wide range of interpretations of its contents.

The last version DigComp 2.2 [5] did not really change the framework but provided 260 new examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes for the existing 21 competences, and added new and emerging trends such as systems driven by artificial intelligence (AI) or digital accessibility among them. The examples of skills, attitudes and knowledge created through the collaborative work of a varied set of experts provide extra guidelines for the application of the framework: they illustrate how competences become more tangible in specific statements, helping to get more homogeneity in the practical implementation. Following this line of action, JRC has been developing a work on learning outcomes (LO) linked to DigComp 2.2 through a compilation of examples voluntarily provided by relevant stakeholders across Europe. Those LO have been analyzed by a group of qualified experts, explicitly invited for that among known experienced ones. The results are still under development at the present time, so practitioners do not have yet extra guidance for the application of the framework.

One additional development related to the context of DigComp was the project for a feasibility study of a European Digital Skills Certificate (EDSC)¹. Although it would support recognition of digital skills in Europe and the final report was published, there have not been implementation decisions for certification of digital skills, so this strong mechanism to measure the development of skills is not uniformly available in the EU to guide the implementation of the framework.

As commented above, Digcomp was originally created as a reference for digital competence for all citizens without a clear direct link to the job market. Despite previous attempts already commented, this aspect remains scarcely developed. Recently, JRC has opened new perspectives thanks to a recent study to map the DigComp competences to ESCO² skills [6]. This mapping enables the use of the huge amount of information generated by other EU initiatives using the ESCO terminology as basis. Of course, as first contribution, the study is not definitive and does

¹ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/scientific-activities-z/education-and-training/digital-transformation-education/digital-competence-framework-citizens-digcomp/european-digital-competence-certificate-edsc_en

² <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

not explore all the possibilities applicable to this approach, but it provides useful insights on the role of the digital skills within the labor market and the ESCO classification, a compulsory labor classification for all Member States of the EU from 2021. It is a reference automatically understandable in all countries, thus giving extra value to all developments based on it.

This situation in these two aspects has motivated this work with the following research questions:

- RQ1: Can an analysis of the contents of the DigComp framework version 2.2 provide relevant information for its understanding and application?
- RQ2: Can the links between DigComp and ESCO enable the use of open sources of information on the labor market for a study of the demand of digital skills in occupations?

This communication is structured as follows: Section 2 will present the analysis of contents and text of the version 2.2 of DigComp while Section 3 will describe its link to the labor market using ESCO. Finally, Section 4 will summarize the conclusions and will depict some promising subsequent lines of research.

2. ANALYSIS OF DIGCOMP

The structure of DigComp 2.2 [5] is well known: 5 competence areas (Dimension 1), 21 competences (Dimension 2), 8 possible proficiency levels (Dimension 3), 260 examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes (Dimension 4) and Use cases (Dimension 5). Although this information has served as basis for many developments, it is possible to get more insights into the concepts through an analysis of the text of the contents. The use of keywords and verbs is a technique for qualitative analysis of text and text mining to extract new knowledge and insights from models and documents. Verbs (as shown by [7]) are normally very relevant as well as the most frequent words in text. We have analyzed the text of all the contents of the DigComp structure combining text mining and natural language processing (NLP), previously creating a database with all the elements thus giving more flexibility for the analysis. This pretends to offer some first answers to RQ1. The results show how each competence has different frequent words in its whole text content (description, examples, etc.), once cleaned the not relevant words like articles, etc. A partial example is shown in Table 1 (not all 21 competencies due to space reasons). It is also possible to analyze the type of verbs allocated to the examples in the different proficiency levels of DigComp. As shown in Figure 2 with a partial example (the whole table has 53 rows), the use of the verbs does not clearly differentiate the ones allocated to each level (despite the normal use of verbs in Bloom's taxonomy [7]). Of course, much deeper and extensive analysis is possible thanks to the development of a database with all the contents of DigComp.

Table 1. Meaningful frequent words for some competences of DigComp.

DigComp Skill	Meaningful Words
1.1 BROWSING, SEARCHING AND FILTERING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT	['information', 'search', 'content', 'data', 'access', 'user', 'need', 'personal', 'find', 'identify', 'navigate', 'strategy']
1.2 EVALUATING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT	['information', 'content', 'data', 'source', 'reliability', 'credibility', 'evaluation', 'analysis', 'credible', 'critically']
1.3 MANAGING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT	['data', 'environment', 'organise', 'content', 'information', 'structured', 'retrieve', 'problem', 'level', 'need', 'online']
2.1 INTERACTING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	['communication', 'appropriate', 'context', 'mean', 'technology', 'given', 'interact', 'problem', 'select', 'variety', 'level']
2.2 SHARING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	['share', 'content', 'information', 'technology', 'appropriate', 'sharing', 'practice', 'attribution', 'referencing', 'data']
2.3 ENGAGING CITIZENSHIP THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	['society', 'participate', 'service', 'technology', 'citizen', 'appropriate', 'empower', 'level', 'citizenship']

Table 2. Use of some verbs in the examples of DigComp.

Levels	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
choose	3	3	0	0	0	2	1	0
describe	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
detect	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
differentiate	3	3	1	1	1	0	0	0
find	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
identify	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
list	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
recognize	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
select	2	2	2	5	0	0	0	0
show	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	0
follow	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

3. LINKING DIGCOMP TO LABOR MARKET AND USING OSINT

Although the term OSINT is normally linked to the concept of intelligence as collection of information of military or political value, its concept can be applied to any method of gathering information from public or other open sources with the purpose of answering a specific question. There are several examples of available open sources of data on the labor market: e.g., online job ads as well as reports, studies and databases reflecting the opinion of experts. In the context of the EU, there are two extraordinarily open sources of information: the own ESCO database and the OVATE³ tool developed by CEDEFOP⁴, one of the EU's decentralized agencies aimed at

³ <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/skills-online-vacancies>

⁴ <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en>

supporting the vocational education and training (VET) policies. What each of these two sources can provide is different but complementary and useful.

The first version of ESCO was developed during four years with the participation of more than 200 experts from all sectors with the support of consultants and it is regularly updated. It expresses the qualitative vision of experts, usually better for identifying trends and reviewing the value of data. The direct use of the ESCO database (more than 3000 occupations and nearly 14000 skills and knowledge items) through the website is not efficient or feasible. So, we used a local replica of the database, recreated by us with data downloaded from the website.

The OVATE tool is fed by a powerful system that applies web scraping from a myriad of job portals across Europe to collect millions of job ads, classifying them according to the ESCO concepts and terminology using text mining and AI. The result is the generation and classification of datasets with millions of job ads per semester. Even considering possible errors during the process, the representativeness of this data could be hardly discussed, especially when compared to other studies with small samples. The use of job ads for research has a long tradition [8] and provided good results although it has limitations and threats to validity, especially when methodological guides are neglected. The possible limitations are:

- Not all vacancies are publicly available on job portals and open sources of information:
 - The scarce tradition in publicity of vacancies in some sectors or groups of occupations. For example, OVATE datasets do not have any job ads for the group of occupations “63 - Subsistence farmers, fishers, hunters and gatherers”.
 - Some types of vacancies, e.g. high level managerial or qualified positions, are treated confidentially, with headhunting services or within private specialized communities.
 - Some employers do not request external candidates or do not use ads for recruitment as they use internal promotion of employees or direct relations with interested people.
- Some vacancies could have been published on different sites or channels thus multiplying its presence in statistics unless careful cleaning of data avoids it.
- The job ads and their description texts are not always accurate:
 - The terms used for description are not precise or even incorrectly written (although automated text analysis can partially fix this: see e.g. [9])
 - The employers are not always expressing all the requirements they consider relevant for a position, either because they consider some of them implicit or because they forget to include them or make mistakes when writing the text.

- Employers are sometime adding requirements that are not necessary for the position, either because they include trendy terms and buzzwords popular at the time or because they request more than needed to get more qualified candidates.
- Unless we can use temporal series of data sets, the analysis cannot easily detect trends. Even in that case, it is not sure that prediction of future needs can be forecasted from job ads data while human experts can probably be better for that.

In our analysis of the labor market with these two sources of information, ESCO database and OVATE, we have adopted a more restricted approach in identifying the ESCO skills that can be equivalent (or assimilated) to the ones of DigComp when compared to [6]: JRC consider both skills with explicit or implicit digital focus (i.e. explicitly mentioning digital environment, not explicitly mentioning digital context but requiring elements of digital environment). In our case, we only used the ones with explicit relations to digital competences of DigComp.

Another relevant point in our analysis refers to the exclusion of the groups of ICT occupations, namely groups “133. Information and communications technology service managers”, “25. Information and communications technology professionals” and “35. Information and communications technicians”. The debate on the fuzzy border between highest levels of DigComp and the lowest levels of competence of ICT professionals (e.g., as expressed in the standard EN16234 or e-CF [10]) is not yet solved but, although these professionals may also need digital user skills, the focus is on the qualified professional competences. As we will see this can affect the analysis of data to distinguish which are really DigComp skills.

We will start our analysis with the data extracted from the ESCO database. They express how many occupations in each occupation group include DigComp competences in the corresponding recommended profile. We will use the same mapping presented in [6] using only the explicit skills, noting that the mapping does not show any relation with ESCO skills for “2.5 Netiquette (online etiquette)”, “2.6 Managing digital identity”, “4.3 Protecting health and well-being” or “4.4 Protecting the environment”. We will not address or question this point in our work. The mapping does not clearly distinguish if the skills correspond to the expected levels of DigComp or if some skills are mainly linked to IT professionals: this is particularly frequent in the skills in “3.4 Programming” (1969 pairs out of 6272 in total). The occupations also include the ones for IT professionals (ESCO groups 133, 25, and 35). Moreover, many items on technologies and languages multiply the number of occurrences of skills in occupations. Despite this, the results on skills and knowledge from DigComp competencies in occupations are in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of different occupations recommending each DigComp competence

As we can see, many DigComp competences are not present in the recommended profiles while others have a wide presence in the global set of occupations. The results are not restricted to non-ICT occupations, noting the big amount corresponding to ICT occupations, with very qualified skills in 3.4 Programming, a category overrepresented in these statistics. This will be refined in the next versions of the analysis for a better vision of the demand of Digcomp.

Figure 2. Percentage of Online Jo Ads that mention skills linked to each DigComp competence

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

As seen, the analysis of both the contents of DigComp and of its link to the labor market is not easy. Researchers need to ensure accuracy and consider many limitations and risks before generating conclusions. However, these aspects are totally necessary for a pragmatic solid application of the framework, valid for the labor market and more consistent in education and training. This work represents an initial advance towards more detailed and precise information for the application of DigComp. On one hand, the analysis of the contents of DigComp might serve for a better understanding of the concepts of all dimensions of the framework and help to a more homogeneous application in practice. On the other hand, a clearer link between DigComp and the labor market requires an extensive study of open sources of information that provide evidence of the reality while also needing experts to complete the interpretation of results. However, the big numbers in data samples, the variety of data sources and the application of solid methods for analysis, including text mining and NLP among others, are essential for trustable information. Of course, it is needed a good exploration of the highest levels of DigComp and their differences and similarities with the items described by the standard EN 16234 to clarify the borders between both frameworks, avoiding possible confusions and risky assumptions in analysis and among not qualified experts.

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A Cross–Country Examination of Digital Literacy in Europe Based on the Digcomp Framework

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INTRODUCTION

As digitalization permeates all aspects of work, education, and social interaction, the ability to use digital technologies becomes increasingly important [1]. Successfully navigating the digital world requires digital literacy and a lack thereof can negatively impact an individual's life [2], [3]. Differential levels of digital literacy within a population - so called digital divides - are associated with various individual and societal risks, such as social inequality or reduced innovative and economic strength in affected countries [4]. The European Commission tackles these issues by targeted policy interventions to increase digital literacy of EU citizens and society at large [5]. The project at hand aims to expand the empirical foundation of such targeted measures by gathering and analyzing representative data on digital skills across Europe. Corresponding findings can help shape the digital future of society.

METHOD

To examine digital skills in an EU cross-country perspective, the authors conducted seven large-scale representative population surveys in Germany (n= 9.044), Austria (n = 1.157), France (n = 1.715), Finland (n = 1.207), Italy (n = 1.734), the U.K (n = 1.548) and Spain (n = 1.690). Digital skills were measured by employing the DigCompSAT self-reflection tool [6]. This research closes a gap in empirical knowledge about digital skills in Europe as it provides the first representative data based on the Digital Competence Framework for European [7] for the observed countries. A mixed sampling strategy with online and telephone interviews was applied in order to allow for representative analyses including individuals with no access to the internet.

FINDINGS

The results show that digital literacy differs considerably between observed countries, with Finland scoring highest and Germany, Italy and Spain lowest. All countries displayed considerable gaps of digital literacy between different sociodemographic groups. Younger individuals aged 14 to 29 years generally display substantially higher levels of digital literacy than older individuals.

Similarly, highly educated individuals achieve better levels of digital literacy than persons with a low formal education in almost all countries. Lastly, gender differences are small, but consistently appear in all cases, with slightly better results among men than women. The described differences vary across the observed countries. In Germany, the digital divides based on age and gender are largest - complemented by a relatively large education-based digital literacy gap. When it comes to education, the corresponding digital divide is highest in Spain, but almost non-existent in Finland. This is accompanied by comparatively small gender- and age-based digital divides in the Finnish population.

CONCLUSION

The authors have identified several digital divides within and between observed countries. Overall low digital literacy in Germany, Italy and Spain indicate that targeted measures to promote literacy in these countries seem sensible in order to compensate cross-national digital divides. Additionally the observed digital divides between social groups within countries highlight the need to promote digital literacy especially among female individuals and persons who are older and less well educated. This especially true for Germany, where digital literacy seems to be more dependent on socio-structural factors, resulting in a particularly high risk for large sections of the population to fall behind digitally. In contrast to that, the comparatively good digital literacy and small digital divides in Finland underscore the country's position as a digital frontrunner in Europe. At ICODSIP the authors would like to discuss the application of the DigComp-Framework as well as the findings and its implications in more detail.

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SME Digital Maturity Upskilling and Accelerator Program with the University of Botswana Innovation Centre

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INTRODUCTION

The SME Digital Maturity Upskilling and Accelerator Program aims to enhance the digital capabilities of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Botswana. The goal of the project is to create and launch specific practical further training and accelerator programs to support the digitalisation of Botswana SMEs. Running from May 1, 2024, to May 31, 2025, this initiative is led by BCS Digital Skills Academy (BCS Koolitus AS) in close partnership with the University of Botswana Innovation Centre(UBIC). Botswana has a digital transformation strategy[1] aligned with the digital transformation strategy for Africa[2] which is part of a wider goal to move Botswana from a middle to a high-income country by 2036[3]. This project contributes to these goals by enhancing digital capacity and skills within the SME sector in Botswana. The BCS Digital Skills Academy has recently completed a similar project in Namibia and the wider team also includes experts who participated in the recent development of the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens of Botswana so there was an existing basis of skills and relationships.

WORK PACKAGES

The project consists of six work packages: WP1: Competence Needs and Curriculum Development; WP2: Creation of the Training Programs; WP3:Creation of the Core Learning Units for Digitalisation Leaders Program; WP4: Piloting and Sustainability Assurance of the Project Results; WP5: Communication;WP6: Project Management, described as follows. In collaboration with UBIC a competence profile (WP1) necessary for the target group has been created. This was based on the EU ICT Role Profiles [4] and also guided by more recent work providing guidance on

developing curricula from Role Profiles[5] , along with a curriculum and the required learning outcomes. Based on the curriculum, two programs are currently being developed (WP2): a shorter 8-day further training program for company managers, and a longer 3–6-month accelerator program for company teams. The usefulness of the longer-term accelerator program providing ongoing support had been established through experience of recent similar project by BCS in Namibia. The training modules including time and activity plans with theory blocks, practical exercises, discussions, and debates are currently under development. The most important part of the educational material, where international experience is presented, will be delivered in the form of video lectures using modern AI video generators. A co-creation workshop (WP3) to discuss current draft content with UBIC and other stakeholders is taking place in November 2024 to coincide with Innovation Week in Botswana. Pilot training and train-the-trainer seminars will then be carried out in March 2024 (WP4) to test the developed program and materials and hand them over to UBIC.

CONCLUSION

Sustainability has been carefully considered in terms of partner choice and alignment with existing strategy in Botswana. The Innovation Centre's interest and ability to take over and continue the program is deemed the best in Botswana with high levels of expertise and excellent relationships with relevant partners. The connection with the University ensures knowledge of the field and the availability of competent lecturers. The Centre's close cooperation with key institutions, such as the Local Enterprise Authority and Botswana Digital Innovation Hub also creates direct opportunities for securing future program funding.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Evaluating Digital Skills in EU Countries

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INTRODUCTION

Appropriate skills and knowledge are very important in order to be able to deal with new technologies in an informed and thoughtful manner in private and professional life. In the long term, a lack of digital competence among the population jeopardizes a country's technological ability to compete as a business location. In order to gather comprehensive data on digital skills the Bavarian Research Institute for Digital Transformation (bidt) started the bidt-Digitalbarometer. The project aims to gather data from representative population surveys on the digital transformation in Germany and other European comparison countries with the main focus on digital skills. After a first wave of surveys was conducted in seven countries, currently the second survey wave for Germany is prepared extending the original assessment of digital skills with new items referring to digital skills in dealing with artificial intelligence.

Scope of the project

The project conducts large scale population surveys dealing with various topics of the digital transformation. However, its main focus is on digital skills. The project was the first to collect representative data with the self-reflection tool DigCompSAT for the European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens [1] in Germany, Austria, France, Finland, Italy, the United Kingdom and Spain. For the first wave of surveys a mixed sampling strategy with online and telephone interviews was chosen in order to allow for representative analyses including also persons with no access to the internet. Table 1 shows the sample characteristics of the first wave of surveys [2], [3].

Table 1. Project's first wave of surveys

	Germany	Austria	France	Finland	Italy	U.K.	Spain
Survey period from/to	09/08/21–13/09/21	14/11/22–21/12/22	21/11/22–05/01/23	28/11/22–05/01/23	21/11/22–05/01/23	21/11/22–05/01/23	21/11/22–05/01/23
n Total	9.044	1.157	1.715	1.207	1.734	1.698	1.690
n CAWI	7.644	1.032	1.565	1.082	1.534	1.548	1.540
n CATI	1.400	125	150	125	200	150	150

Previous results

The first surveys showed significant differences in digital skills according to people's socio-demographic characteristics within a country and across countries. For example, compared to other countries, digital skill gaps by age and gender were considerably large in Germany.

Next steps / Work packages

Currently the second survey wave in Germany is prepared where the original DigCompSAT will be enriched with additional items referring to digital skills in dealing with artificial intelligence and generative artificial intelligence. For this purpose, first 60 new items were developed out of an extensive literature review. These items follow the DigCompSAT structure and also cover the types knowledge, skills, and attitude. In a second step, these items will be tested in an online pre-study helping to select a small number of items to be included in the next Digitalbarometer survey wave. The next survey wave will then again consist of an online survey and additional telephone interviews. Table 2 lists the next steps.

Table 2. Next steps

Work package	Time frame	Anticipated No. of Obs.	Main content
Online survey (pre-study)	Q4/2024	1.500	60 Competence items dealing with AI for selection for the next Digitalbarometer survey wave
Digitalbarometer survey wave in Germany	Q1/2025	CAWI: 7.600 CATI: 1.400	82 DigCompSAT items + selected AI competence items (among other questions)
Report with results and analyses	Q2-Q3/2025		Analyses, findings an implication of the Digitalbarometer survey wave

Conclusion

The previous findings allowed detailed analyses of the distribution of digital skills in the population and help to develop better targeted programs to certain groups in society in order to close the skill gap and prevent that certain groups are left behind permanently. The continuation of the project will allow to monitor changes in digital skills over time and therefore to assess the effectiveness of certain programs aiming to strengthen digital skills. New survey waves will also allow to include new skills as technologies like artificial intelligence evolve. The project expands the empirical knowledge on digital skills, helps to initiate debates and allows to base decisions in order to shape the digital future of society in a responsible and public interest-oriented manner on empirical evidence.

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ComeThinkAgain – COMputational and Entrepreneurship THINKing And Green Agenda INnovations

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INTRODUCTION

Digitization and production innovations in combination with the ongoing climate change pose many challenges for our private but also the professional life. Specifically, education systems and the labor market have to address new demands while also facing new challenges, such as defining these skills and implementing teaching methods to acquire them. In this context, the European Commission calls for new skills to keep the EU's labor market competitive [1]. The recently started Erasmus+ project "ComeThinkAgain" (CTA)¹ aims to address these challenges by fostering a strategic collaboration between Higher Education (HE), Vocational Education and Training (VET), enterprises, and research organizations. One of the main outcomes of the project is the development, implementation and evaluation of a cross-sectoral, standardized training and certification system called **CTA-CETS (Certification based Education Training System)** for the three areas ('pillars') of 1) Computational Thinking Skills (CT), 2) Entrepreneurship Education & Innovation Skills (EE) as well as 3) Social Responsibility, Sustainability & Green Skills (GS). ComeThinkAgain is co-funded by the European Union (ERASMUS-EDU-2023-PI-ALL-INNO) and includes project partners from Austria (University of Teacher Education Styria, Austrian Computer Society), Switzerland (University of Teacher Education Zurich), Germany (Gesellschaft für Informatik), Estonia (University of Tartu), Finland (University of Oulu), Denmark (Mercantec), Belgium (The Square Dot Team), Spain (Grupo Inmark) and Ireland (Konnektable Technologies).

¹ <https://comethinkagain.eu/>

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

Active teachers, vocational education trainers equip future workers with the necessary skills, therefore a train-the-trainer approach is one of the central methods applied in the project. The CTA-CETS is inspired by the concept of the International Certification of Digital Literacy (ICDL) and relies on well-proven methodologies and concepts such as blended-learning, e-learning, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), nano-degrees and micro-certifications embedded into a state-of-the-art learning management system (LMS). The project is organized in five highly interrelated operational and supporting work packages (project management, content creation, piloting and evaluation, implementation, dissemination). Data collection for the evaluation is done using a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative measures. Data is analyzed accordingly using descriptive and inferential statistics as well as content analysis and triangulation [2].

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS, CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project started in Q2 2024 and is currently in its initial stage of setting the ground, performing related research, establishing an External Advisory Board and organizing co-creation workshops with stakeholders. One of the most relevant results of the project is the Certification based Education Training System (ComeThinkAgain-CETS) including curricula and learning material for the three pillars CT, EE and GS in alignment with the three major European reference frameworks, the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp), the Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp) as well as the European Sustainability Competence Framework (EntreComp). Pilot implementations and evaluations of CETS with the target group, in collaboration with project-internal but also external HEs and VET providers across five European countries, will ensure high quality, solid validation, and broad acceptance.

Acknowledgment: Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the EACEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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D-PAIDEIA. Pedagogical Digital Competences as a key element for the digital transformation

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INTRODUCTION

The project *101087643 D-Paideia. Pedagogical Digital Competences as a key element for the digital transformation* is an ERASMUS-LS project that addresses the need to work on pedagogical digital competences (PDC) as a result of the transformation of teaching and learning processes as evidenced by the COVID-19 pandemic and emergency remote learning [1]. To this end, a 36-month Project is presented, formed by a consortium of 6 partners: Action Synergy (Greece), Università degli Studi di Firenze (Italy), Universitat de Girona (Spain), Centar Za Tvorchesko Obuchenie (Bulgaria), UC Leuven and All Digital (Belgium). The main objective of the project is the development of a pedagogical guide on the update of the digital competence framework, and the impact on 100 schools as a result. To achieve this objective, the project has been divided into 7 work packages (WP).

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

The Project is constituted of 7 WP: Project Management and Evaluation; Development of a Qualification Framework for Pedagogical Digital Competencies; Development of a Curriculum for the Pedagogical Digital Competences; Pedagogical Digital Strategies in Educational Institutions; Piloting of the Qualification Profile and the Curriculum; Transfer of Results to Policy and Practitioner Level, and Dissemination

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

Although only halfway through the project, D-Paideia has so far offered relevant results which can be synthesized as the following.

D-Paideia highlights the need for an update within the DigCompEdu framework that emphasizes the extension of DigCompEdu Area 1 considering: 1.5. *Awareness of institutional policy*, 1.6. *Attitude towards the adoption of digital technologies*, and 1.7. *Digital work-life balance and wellbeing*. The replacement in the Area 6 of *Responsible Use for Safety* (6.4); and the new area 7: *Socio-Emotional and Relational Skills* that include: 7.1. *Managing educational relationships with ICT*; 7.2. *Diverse and flexible facilitation strategies*; and 7.3. *Digital Identity and reputation management*. [2] [3]

This update has been validated by 30 experts [3], and positively received by teachers [4]. Furthermore, teachers have also positively assessed the learning objectives, and the curriculum developed in the WP3.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The study was conducted within the Erasmus+ project D-Paideia “Pedagogical Digital Competences as a key element for the digital transformation” (2023-2025). The European Commission’s support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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Figure 1. Work Packages of D-PAIDEA project and their main objectives

WP	Name	Main Objectives
1	Project Management and Evaluation	- Task planning, project meetings, reporting
2	Development of a Qualifications Framework for PDC	- Update and Adaptation of the DigCompEdu framework taken into consideration the experience of the covid19 pandemic period [2] - Creation of a framework that will include in the digital environment skills related with social and emotional learning and new pedagogical approaches [3] [4]
3	Development of a Curriculum for the PDC	- To develop a curriculum in order to develop the pedagogical digital competencies of the teachers - To identify and develop training materials that could support the teachers in the improvement of their pedagogical digital competencies
4	Pedagogical Digital Strategies in Educational Institutions	- Support the development and adoption of the pedagogical digital strategies in educational institutions - Support the development of a whole school approach in the development of pedagogical digital skills of the teachers
5	Piloting of the Qualification Profile and the Curriculum	- Test and evaluate the impact of the qualification profile and curriculum - Develop the pedagogical digital skills
6	Transfer of Results to Policy and Practitioner Level	- Transfer the project results to policy makers & academics - Mainstream project results - Create a network of initial and continuous teacher training organizations that would incorporate this framework in their own teaching curricula
7	Dissemination	Raise awareness about the project

Digital Transformation of a Public Administration – Lessons Learnt

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INTRODUCTION

This paper reports some interesting outcomes of a single sub-project that involved the authors, within a plan by the Regional Government of [Liguria](#) funded through “Next Generation EU”.

1000 Experts

In 2021 the European Union created the Recovery and Resilience Facility and allocated a maximum programme envelope of €806.9 billion. The Italian Government launched a [National Plan for Recovery and Resilience](#) and negotiated loans for €122.6 bn plus grants for €71.8 bn. In such context, under Mission 1, Component 1 (Digitalisation, innovation and security in Public Administration), Sub-investment 2.2.1, €0.3 bn were allocated to select and engage 1000 professionals (engineers, architects, scientists, managers, data experts) to provide a competent support to the Local Governments in simplifying procedures, clearing backlog, and improving efficiency through a permanent reduction of throughput time (i.e. the time it takes to complete a formal procedure, from citizen’s request to its outcome). The first author was selected as a consultant and assigned to the Information Systems Unit led by the second author.

Phytosanitary sector

Directive [2009/128/EC](#) aims to achieve a sustainable use of pesticides in the EU by reducing the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment; the primary action descending from this directive relates to training of users, advisors and distributors of pesticides; the Italian law n. 150/2012 assigns each Regional Administration the task to train and authorise users of any phytosanitary product; therefore, Regione Liguria has a [phytosanitary department](#), also due to the importance of flower production in local economy. The official target of the dematerialisation sub-project in such department is to reduce throughput time by 15% in 30 months (before end of June 2025).

WORK PACKAGES AND MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

The (huge) improvement project in Liguria and its work packages are described in the [Integrated Plan of Tasks and Organisation](#)¹, which can not be synthesised here in few lines. Referring to the single sub-project, a new digitised procedure is now used to release phytosanitary authorisations (1,452 cases since end October 2023). The average throughput time was reduced by 33%, from 19.7 to 13.2 days; a further 4÷6% reduction is now expected.

The importance of measurement

Regione Liguria included the procedure for phytosanitary authorisations in the set of high priority improvements targeted by the *1000 Esperti* project; when this choice was made, the Administration feared that this procedure was at risk to exceed maximum response time allowed by law (90 days) simply because they were aware of few cases of serious delay, and there were no simple means to measure average response times.

The dark (less known) side of digital transformation

In traditionally organised bureaucracy, some fuzzy areas may survive; although law 241/90 (in force for over 3 decades) defines a precise regulation for administrative procedures, some concepts are not always put into practice in a rigorous manner: the applicant presenting a request must be legally identified (even if the case refers to another person, who authorised the applicant); a single officer in charge of the request must be identified, and the citizen must be informed about this; if the application is not complete, the case can be formally suspended; the citizen must be informed of the main steps and of the final outcome of the procedure. When implementing such rules through an IT system, some solutions based on “common sense” must be abandoned; e.g. the digital identity of each party (applicant and officer in charge of responding) can no longer be blurred into an anonymous “office” or group of people. If citizens are not confident enough to use digital systems when submitting a request, they can still (in most cases) authorise somebody else to apply in their name, but this can become a dangerous and complicated “alienation” (e.g. what happens if the delegate dies?)

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We pointed out some specific reasons why the need for digital skills and for a deeper understanding among IT professionals and across all citizens of the impacts of digital transformation grows with the renewal of public services; the value of Next Generation EU support for such transformation is evident.

¹ See page 98 for targets referring to the phytosanitary procedure, page 102 to link with digital competences of personnel, page 110 and subsequent (PNRR measure 1.7.2) for some actions aimed at improving citizens' skills.

DigitALL: Training and certification in digital competencies within the DigComp framework.

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INTRODUCTION

The DigitALL project aims to promote digital competencies among citizens, especially within the university community, through training and certification using the European Union's DigComp framework. Coordinated by the University of Castilla-La Mancha, and with the collaboration of 22 Spanish universities, this project is a key initiative in Spain's efforts to ensure digital inclusion and competence for all citizens. The project is supported by the *Plan Unidigital*, a national strategy aimed at boosting digital transformation in higher education.

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

The DigitALL project is structured around several key work packages that aim to develop high-quality educational content and tools for the certification of digital skills. Weekly coordination meetings were held every Monday to ensure smooth collaboration among all participating universities, enabling continuous progress and effective communication.

1. Development of Training Materials: The project has created 756 educational videos, each averaging six minutes, accompanied by 1,260 pages of documentation. These materials are designed to cover the 21 competencies defined by DigComp, across six proficiency levels (A1 to C2).
2. Creation of a Question Bank: The project has developed a question bank containing 10,800 questions. These include multiple-choice questions, true/false questions, and practical exercises that evaluate both theoretical knowledge and practical skills.
3. Certification Platform: The project includes the development of an innovative platform that facilitates the semi-automated generation of exams for the certification of digital competencies. This platform is designed to be user-friendly, scalable, and accessible,

ensuring a seamless certification process for all participants. This platform ensures an accessible and efficient certification process, making it possible for individuals to obtain certification remotely. It is also funded through a fee-for-exam model, which supports its long-term sustainability.

4. Inclusion and Accessibility: The training materials are being translated into Catalan, Basque, and Galician, reflecting the linguistic diversity of Spain and ensuring that all citizens have equal access to learning and certification opportunities.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

By 2024, DigitALL is expected to deliver significant results, including:

1. The completion of all self-paced learning materials by October 2024.
2. The full development of the question bank by December 2024.
3. The operational certification platform, ready by early 2025, will allow for remote testing and certification, enabling citizens to validate their digital competencies effectively.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The DigitALL project will serve as a comprehensive evaluation and certification tool within the DigComp framework, offering citizens, particularly in the university community, a clear path to assess and validate their digital skills. Backed by European funding and structured for sustainability through an exam fee model, DigitALL is designed to continue impacting digital literacy beyond its initial implementation. Additionally, the project model is adaptable and can be replicated by other countries to enhance their citizens' digital skills. The completion of these tools will play a crucial role in driving digital inclusion and literacy across Spain, ensuring that citizens are prepared to thrive in a digitally integrated society.

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Exploring the new field of skills in digital for sustainability

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INTRODUCTION

The Digital4Sustainability project is a pioneering initiative aimed at accelerating Europe's twin transition by equipping the workforce with the necessary skills to boost sustainability-driven innovation. Recognising the pressing need to meet climate neutrality objectives and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the project will develop a forward-thinking Digital Sustainability Skills Strategy as well as VET / HE Learning Programmes that will address the urgent and emerging skills needs of industry in the key areas of digital & sustainability.

Digital4Sustainability is funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union under the Alliances for Innovation call (Project number: 101140316). This 4-year project brings together 29 members of the Digital Large-Scale Partnership under the Pact for Skills from 13 EU countries. The consortium includes digital and sustainability experts, business associations, universities, and Vocational Education and Training (VET) providers. These partners are Adecco Holding, Adecco Training, BadgeBox, BASSCOM, BCS Koolitus, Cefriel, ClujIT, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia (GZS CCIS), Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia - Institute for Business Education (GZS CPU), DIGITALEUROPE, Digital Technology Skills Ltd, Eduserpro, European DIGITAL SME Alliance, Fast Lane, IVSZ- ICT Association of Hungary, Matrix Internet, National College of Ireland, Profil Klett, TEKenable, Universidad Internacional de La Rioja (UNIR), University of Alcalá (UAH), University of Applied Sciences Utrecht (HU), University of Koblenz, POLITEHNICA Bucharest, CEPIS, Fraunhofer Institute for Software and Systems Engineering ISST, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM), INFOBALT, Skillnet Ireland.

By aligning with market and industry needs, the project will ensure that its training programmes address both current and future skill needs. A key focus is on empowering European Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), positioning them as key drivers of sustainable digital innovation. SMEs will benefit from customised on-the-job training designed to strengthen their capacity to develop sustainable technologies that support Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices.

Ultimately, Digital4Sustainability will not only support Europe's climate neutrality ambitions but will also contribute to the long-term competitiveness and growth of its economy, ensuring that the workforce is prepared for the challenges and opportunities of a sustainable digital future.

PROCESS

The project started this year and the main focus content-wise is Work Package 2 “*Needs Analysis & Digital Sustainability Skills Strategy for Europe*”. The needs analysis was the first step in this process and consisted of a multi-method approach to identify the roles, skills, and education and training needs with regard to digital solutions supporting sustainability. Desk research was used to find and analyse labour market reports, and to execute a literature review on the theoretical state of the art of the field of digital for sustainability and draw conclusions from relevant scientific literature. A questionnaire sent out to all sorts of organisations was used to study the market demand for roles and skills in the field. National expert panels in the consortium countries provided qualitative input on roles, skills and education & training. Already available learning programmes were identified by conducting desk research. Finally, an EU expert panel was held to validate the results of the data collection. Triangulation between the results of the individual methods resulted in overall conclusions on the current and expected future roles and skills needs.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

The results will provide a much-needed baseline for evidence and future activities in the emerging field of skills for digital sustainability.

To facilitate the needs analysis, a framework of digital4sustainability roles was developed starting from the CEN ICT professional role profiles based on the e-CF. The needs analysis confirmed the relevance of the framework, with the remark that it should be clear to people that roles are different from jobs, and roles in this field will in a substantial part of the cases be fulfilled by people who also have other roles in the organisation.

The analysis shows that the most important skills in the short term are related to reporting and legislation, like for example ESG reporting. Also, data-related skills, like data analysis, are considered important.

In general, awareness raising training on digital for sustainability for managers, but also for technical personnel like software developers, is considered the main issue that needs to be addressed urgently.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The needs analysis is the starting point for developing the Digital4Sustainability skills strategy and digital4sustainability learning programmes, starting with urgent upskilling programmes that will address the most urgent skills needs. These will focus on awareness raising, data-related skills, and reporting and legislation. After that, the project will switch to the learning programmes needed in the long run to make sure that there are people to design, develop and deploy digital solutions for sustainability issues. This project is co-funded by the European Commission, as part of the Erasmus+ programme and is one of the so-called Blueprint projects.

Adapting DigComp for asylum seekers in Germany – The DigiQ Projects

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INTRODUCTION

With the aim of improving the digital skills of asylum seekers during their first weeks in Germany a team from the Business Informatics and Media Management research group at Mainz University of Applied Sciences conducted the DigiQ 1-3 projects. They were “Digitalisierung verstehen und anwenden: Konzeption, Durchführung und Evaluation von Lehrveranstaltungen für die digitale Qualifizierung rückkehrinteressierter Migrant*innen” (01.04.2022-30.06.2023, ID: 20.2045.1-006.01), „DigiQ2 - Fortführung digitaler Qualifizierung für rückkehrinteressierte Migrant*innen in der Aufnahmeeinrichtung für Asylbegehrende (AfA) Speyer” (01.07.2023-31.12.2023, ID: 3306-0023#2023/0002-0382 Ref_24) and „DigiQ3 - Fortführung digitaler Qualifizierung für rückkehrinteressierte Migrant*innen in der Aufnahmeeinrichtung für Asylbegehrende (AfA) Speyer” (01.01.2024-30.06.2024, ID: 3306-0023#2023/0002-0382 Ref_24). Over the course of the three DigiQ projects training courses on DigComp skills were designed and implemented for refugees in an initial reception centre in Rhineland-Palatinate. The knowledge acquired by the participants was evaluated.

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

The main process of the project was the creation, implementation, evaluation, and further development of group courses for refugees in the initial reception centre in Speyer, Rhineland-Palatinate. The DigComp 2.2 AT [1] was used as the basis and was initially adapted into a six-week course with all skills areas, and later into two-week modules. Twenty modules were carried out and further developed based on the experience gained during implementation. Participants' knowledge acquisition through the courses was assessed by means of knowledge tests before and after participation.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

DigComp 2.2 AT was initially adapted into one course lasting six weeks in which each competence area was covered in one week with three sessions lasting three hours each. This adaptation turned out not to be useful for the target group. The living conditions in the initial reception centre and the rapid transfers to cities and municipalities that the refugees experience make it almost impossible to participate in educational programmes of this length. The modular concept developed as a result led to more consistent participation. The digital competences were split up in fourteen modules organized in three difficulty levels. Six of those Modules were implemented in a regular course system. The two-week modules now offered focused on individual relevant skills such as online safety or communicating via email and were better adapted to the reality of the refugees' lives. A total of 544 asylum seekers from twenty-seven countries took part in courses, multiple in more than one programme.

As a form of evaluation of the courses, a knowledge level survey was conducted in all courses, which showed that 72% of participants were able to improve their knowledge level because of a course. On average, participants answered 17.2% of the questions on the knowledge test more correctly at the end of the course than at the beginning. During the survey and evaluation, the difficulties of assessing the level of knowledge of digital skills among refugees became clear. These included incomplete data, group work among the participants or the need for translation apps during the tests if a participant's language was not available as a test. These factors weaken the evaluation results.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Adapting a digital competences Framework such as DigComp to a certain target group sometimes needs trial and error. The DigiQ project shows how important it is to subdivide an overall framework to adapt the educational programmes that are to emerge from it to the reality of asylum seekers' lives, which is changing rapidly and constantly. It also highlights the limitations of knowledge assessment in learning with refugees, which will now be used as lessons learnt in subsequent projects to evaluate educational programmes and their impact and to do so in a way that is appropriate for the target group of refugees. The DigiQ projects were funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development via the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH and Rhineland-Palatinate Ministry for Women, Family, Culture, and Integration.

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Digital Competences for Refugees’ Employability: The DigiKoSMos Project

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INTRODUCTION

The project “Digitale Kompetenzen für Selbstbestimmung und Mobilität stärken” (DigiKoSMos, ID: 9168-2023-0571) aims to aid refugees’ global employability and self-determination in Germany by increasing their digital skills. From 1 July 2024 to 30 June 2027 a team from the University of Applied Science in Mainz, Germany, creates, facilitates, and evaluates in-person and online courses in which refugees can increase their digital skills. These educational programmes will be supplemented by accompanying research, information meetings and the provision of all necessary devices, methods, and materials. The courses are run at the initial reception centres for refugees in Rhineland-Palatinate, as well as on an online learning platform.

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

The DigiKoSMos project is divided into five project measures that double as the main work packages. In project measure (PM) 1 ‘In-Person Courses’, scientifically based training courses for refugees are designed, implemented, and continuously developed at their initial reception centres. PM2 ‘Online Courses’ develops online self-study courses for refugees. PM3 ‘Information Meetings’ organises information meetings about the project at the implementation locations. PM4 ‘Training Packages’ includes the compilation of devices, methods, and materials for the project. PM5 ‘Accompanying research’ involves monitoring the project through scientific evaluation and further research.

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS

To lay the foundation for the educational programmes to be designed in PM1 and 2, regional, national, and international competence frameworks were compared, and a project competence framework was compiled with is illustrated in Figure 1. The decisive factor for the compilation was the collection of competence areas from different existing frameworks that could be relevant refugees’ employability.

The core of the DigiKoSMos competence framework is DigComp 2.2 [1], from which all competence areas were taken. Competence area 0 from DigComp 2.3 AT [2] and competence area 6 from the Digital Literacy Global Framework [3] were added.

Figure 1. The DigiKoSMos Digital Competence Framework is compiled out of DigComp 2.3 AT, DigComp 2.2 EU and DLGF

These two added competence areas both serve the needs of the project, its' objectives, and its' target group refugees. The need for education on digital basics such as operating devices is included in competence area zero and the special focus on career-specific competences forms competence area six.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The results of the initial phase of the DigiKoSMos project show how competency frameworks such as DigComp 2.2 can be adapted and compiled for a specific project. Educational programmes for refugees can now be developed based on this adaptation. DigiKoSMos is funded by the European Union through the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund and the Rhineland-Palatinate Ministry for Women, Family, Culture, and Integration.

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